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REMOMEL

D3.2 Report on Staff Exchanges and Summer Schools

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Abbreviations

AI:	Artificial Intelligence
ATU:	Atlantic Technological University
BMI:	Business Model Innovation
BUU:	Bursa Uludag University
PC:	Project Coordinator
PM:	Project Manager
R&I:	Research and Innovation
ULE:	Universidad de León
WP:	Work package

1. Introduction

Strengthening the Research Capacity of Turkey in Innovative Business Models for the Hospitality Sector (REMODEL) project is funded by the European Union Research and Innovation program. The aim of this project is to strengthen the Research and Innovation (R&I) capacity and skills of the members of Bursa Uludağ University (BUU). To achieve this goal, BUU will benefit from the experiences, knowledge, and state-of-the-art tools of its partners, Universidad de Leon (ULE) and Atlantic Technological University (ATU) in Ireland, who are leaders in higher education.

Within the scope of the project, to define a common strategic research agenda and long-term networking and R&I cooperation strategy among REMODEL Partners and key stakeholders, REMODEL summer schools and staff exchange activities will be organised. During the project, each year, one project partner will organize a summer school with an intensive 2-day program. As a result, the project outcomes will be shared with research and scientific communities both in Ireland through ATU, in Spain through ULE, and in Turkey through BUU. Addition to this, qualified academics from ULE and ATU will contribute by giving lectures in BUU doctoral programs as visiting lecturers. With this event, which will last for three years, the project will be promoted and disseminated to different student groups and academic staff. Staff exchanges are deemed fundamental to consolidate research collaboration among REMODEL partners and ensure that knowledge transfer is optimum. Visiting lectures are in the scope of staff exchanges highly contributes to this knowledge transfer.

This report consists of two main sections for staff exchange and summer school activities till M9 of REMODEL. The first section encompasses the staff exchange activities at BUU. In this regard, first, the content of the training provided to doctoral students and academic staff is briefly explained. Subsequently, based on the results of the surveys conducted, the opinions of both the participants and the lecturers regarding the activity are evaluated. The second section covers information related to the REMODEL summer school to be conducted by ULE. The report provides a brief explanation of the instructors and the topics covered in the summer school. Subsequently, it includes information and analyses related to the participants.

2. Staff Exchange Report

2.1. Scope of the Staff Exchange (Trust and Knowledge Management – ATU)

The first REMODEL Visiting Lecture named “trust” and “knowledge management” organized by ATU on April 26th – 27th, 2023, as part of the staff exchanges conducted for the project. This visiting lecture conducted face-to-face and hosted by the BUU Management and Organization PhD class and BUU Business Administration PhD class. The general topics discussed are as follows:

- Embedding trust in our interpersonal and inter-organisational actions
- The importance of proactive knowledge management in contemporary organisations

2.1.1. Visiting Lecturer and Contents

On the first day of the visiting lecture, Dr. Conor McTiernan introduced the topic of trust to PhD students, an increasingly recognised key to understanding employees and customers’ actions and behaviours. On the second day of the visiting lecture, Dr. Conor introduced the topics of knowledge management and absorptive capacity to PhD students, an increasingly recognised key to gaining competitive advantage. During the training teams have been required to complete a brief presentation related to a knowledge transfer and its application to a chosen industry sector.

Conor McTiernan

Conor McTiernan (PhD) is a lecturer in the Department of Tourism and Sport in ATU. He completed his PhD in Leeds Beckett University exploring the role of trust in inter-organisational knowledge transfer in Irish festival and event tourism networks. Conor’s teaching and research primarily focuses on sustainable tourism policy development, tourism networks, innovation, knowledge management and trust in tourism SMTE’s. He is also knowledgeable on tourism network formation and operation; especially facilitating knowledge transfer within network structures. He is a member the Irish Hospitality Institute, the First International Network of Trust and serves as the co-chair on the tourism committee for the Laurentic Forum, a network of Irish, Icelandic, Norwegian and Canadian tourism policy makers and practitioners dedicated to the development of a sustainable tourism sector that supports coastal communities.

The content of the first day of the Conor McTiernan’ visiting lecture was:

- What is trust
- Advantages/ disadvantages of trust
- Barriers and enablers of trust development
- Fragility of trust

Through this content, the following learning outcomes were expected:

- To define trust and understand the importance of trustworthiness
- To differentiate between inter-personal, inter-organisational and political trust
- To appreciate the implications of trust and distrust in inter-personal, inter-organisational and political interactions
- To explore

Dr. Conor talking about "trust"

The content of the second day of the Conor McTiernan' visiting lecture was:

- What is knowledge management
- Types of knowledge – tacit and explicit
- Sources of knowledge
- The challenge of codifying tacit knowledge
- Absorptive capacity, competitive advantage and organisational effectiveness

Through this content, the following learning outcomes are expected:

- To define knowledge and knowledge management
- To differentiate between the types of knowledge and understand how to identify suitable knowledge sources
- To appreciate challenges of codifying tacit knowledge and transferring knowledge
- To explore how absorptive capacity of contemporary organisations can be enhanced

Dr. Conor talking about "knowledge management"

2.1.2. Participants

Visiting lectures are open to participation of all PhD students registered in BUU Social Sciences Institute. 20 PhD students attended the visiting lecture on "trust" held on April 26th, 2023. The distribution of PhD students participating in the visiting lecture by departments and gender are as follows:

<i>Departments of PhD Students Participating in the Visiting Lecture</i>	<i>Numbers</i>
<i>Business Administration</i>	11
<i>Management and Organization</i>	4
<i>Public Finance</i>	2
<i>Econometrics</i>	2
<i>Private Law</i>	1
<i>TOTAL</i>	20

<i>Gender of PhD Students Participating in the Visiting Lecture</i>	<i>Numbers</i>
<i>Male</i>	9
<i>Female</i>	11
<i>TOTAL</i>	20

Dr. Conor and First Day Participants

17 PhD students have been attended the visiting lecture on "knowledge management" held on April 27th, 2023. The distribution of PhD students participating in the visiting lecture by departments and gender are as follows:

<i>Departments of PhD Students Participating in the Visiting Lecture</i>	<i>Numbers</i>
<i>Business Administration</i>	13
<i>Public Finance</i>	2
<i>Econometrics</i>	1
<i>Private Law</i>	1
<i>TOTAL</i>	17

<i>Gender of PhD Students Participating in the Visiting Lecture</i>	<i>Numbers</i>
<i>Male</i>	9
<i>Female</i>	8
<i>TOTAL</i>	17

On the first day, Dr. Conor together with REMODEL Project Coordinator Prof. Aylin Poroy Arsoy and REMODEL WP Leader Prof. Çağatan Taşkın visited BUU Faculty of Economics and Administrative Sciences (FEAS) Dean Prof. Derda Küçükcalp in his office. Dean Küçükcalp stated that as the Faculty they attach importance to the studies carried out within the scope of the REMODEL project, he expressed his pleasure with the visit.

On the second, Dr. Conor together with REMODEL Project Coordinator Prof. Aylin Poroy Arsoy and WP Leaders Prof. Nuran Bayram Arlı, Prof. Çağatan Taşkın, Assoc. Prof. Yasemin Ertan and Assoc. Prof. Elif Yücel visited Bursa Uludag University Rector Prof. Ahmet Saim Kılavuz in his office. Rector Kılavuz stated that his pleasure for Bursa Uludag University, a research university, to take part in such a project and thanked to Dr. Conor for his visit.

2.1.3. Visiting Lecture Evaluation

Visiting lecture evaluation forms were prepared for both participants and the visiting lecturer to evaluate the visiting lecture. At the end of the visiting lecture on both two days, the forms were sent online to the participants and the visiting lecturer. The evaluations of the participants are as follows:

2.1.3.1. Visiting Lecture Evaluation by the Participants

After the visiting lecture on "trust", 6 participants evaluated. The evaluations of the participants are as follows:

Questionnaire	First Day	Second Day
<p>The agenda of the visiting lecture was satisfactory.</p> <p>Strongly agree		
<p>The lecturer was knowledgeable about the visiting lecture topics.</p> <p>Strongly agree		
<p>The lecturer was well prepared.</p> <p>Strongly agree		
<p>The content was well-organised and easy to follow.</p> <p>Strongly agree		
<p>The time allocated for visiting lecture was sufficient.</p> <p>Strongly agree		
<p>The visiting lecture content met my expectations.</p> <p>Strongly agree		

<p>Participation and interaction were encouraged.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ● Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>		
<p>This visiting lecture experience will be useful in my work.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ● Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>		
<p>The venue met all visiting lecture needs.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ● Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>		
<p>I would recommend REMODEL visiting lecture to other people.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ● Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>		
<p>How would you rate the overall organisation of REMODEL visiting lecture (registration, schedule, organisation etc.)</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ● Satisfaction ● Poor ● Very poor ●</p>		
<p>How would you rate the visual of the presentations</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ● Satisfaction ● Poor ● Very poor ●</p>		
<p>How do you rate the quality of presentations</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ● Satisfaction ● Poor ● Very poor ●</p>		

2.1.3.2. Visiting Lecture Evaluation by the Lecturer

After the visiting lectures, here are the evaluations by the visiting lecturer Dr. Conor for both days:

Questionnaire	First Day	Second Day
<p>I had enough time to prepare my presentation.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ●</p> <p>Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>		
<p>The time allowed for the visiting lecture was appropriate.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ●</p> <p>Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>		
<p>The content presented was appropriate to the visiting lecture objectives.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ●</p> <p>Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>		
<p>The content presented was compatible with students' needs.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ●</p> <p>Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>		
<p>The students were interested and enthusiastic.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ●</p> <p>Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>		

<p>I was able to encourage critical thinking and problem-solving.</p> <p>Strongly agree		
<p>The venue met all visiting lecture needs.</p> <p>Strongly agree		
<p>I received positive feedback from faculty members and students after the visiting lecture.</p> <p>Strongly agree		
<p>How do you rate the overall organisation of REMODEL visiting lecture (registration, schedule, communication etc.)</p> <p>Excellent		
<p>How do you rate the overall students' attitudes towards the visiting lecture</p> <p>Excellent		
<p>How do you rate your overall visiting lecture experience</p> <p>Excellent		

2.2. Scope of the Second Staff Exchange (Governance, Ethics and Sustainability and Organizational Culture – ATU)

The second REMODEL Visiting Lecture named “governance, ethics and sustainability” and “organizational culture” organized by ATU on October 4th – 5th, 2023, as part of the staff exchanges conducted for the project. This visiting lecture conducted face-to-face and hosted by the BUU. The general topics discussed are as follows:

- Navigating governance, ethics and sustainability
- Unravelling organisational culture

2.2.1. Visiting Lecturer and Contents

On the first day of the visiting lecture, Dr. Anne Burke explored the topics of governance, ethics, and sustainability with PhD students. By the end of the workshop, students discussed complex issues in these areas and considered these issues in the context of their own research areas. On the second day of the visiting lecture, Dr. Anne introduced the topics of organizational culture and its impact on organisational behaviour, performance, and success to PhD students enabling them to consider these topics as appropriate in the context of their research and future Professional endeavours.

Anne Burke

Dr. Anne Burke is a senior lecturer for Faculty Strategic Development and joint DBA Course Director in the Faculty of Business (Donegal) Atlantic Technological University (ATU). She completed her PhD in Trinity College and has a first-class honours MSc degree in the Management and Application of Information Technology in Accounting from Dublin City University. Anne’s teaching primarily focuses on corporate governance, organisational culture, and audit practice. Anne, a qualified Fellow of the Chartered Association of Certified Accountants (ACCA), enjoyed an 11-year career as an accountant where her work involved auditing, financial accounting, and the implementation of SAP and Agresso ERP systems prior to joining ATU in 2001 as a lecturer.

Since joining ATU in 2001, she has held the roles of Head of Department and Course Director for transformative executive education Master level programmes in Leadership and Innovation for both private and public sectors underpinned by Action Learning. Anne is also a volunteer member of the Society of St. Vincent de Paul and is a non-executive director on the governance boards of the Alcohol Forum and the Donegal Sexual Assault and Rape Crisis Centre.

The following learning outcomes on the first day were expected:

- To describe the role and responsibilities of the board of directors in corporate governance
- To explain how the composition of a board can affect its operation
- To explore the main elements of corporate social responsibility, stakeholder theory, ethics, and sustainability
- To discuss trends in governance, ethics and sustainability

Dr. Anne talking about "governance, ethics and sustainability"

The following learning outcomes on the second day were expected:

- To describe the common characteristics of organisational culture
- To show how culture is transmitted to employees
- To identify the factors that create and sustain an organization's culture
- To compare the functional and dysfunctional effects of organizational culture on people and the organization

Dr. Anne talking about "organisational culture"

2.2.2. Participants

Visiting lectures are open to participation of all PhD students registered in BUU. A total of 19 participants, including 14 PhD students and 5 researchers attended the visiting lecture on "governance, ethics and sustainability" held on October 4th, 2023. The distribution of participants and PhD students participating in the visiting lecture by departments and gender are as follows:

<i>Participants</i>	<i>Numbers</i>
<i>REMODEL researchers</i>	4
<i>Researcher</i>	1
<i>Departments of PhD Students Participating in the Visiting Lecture</i>	<i>Numbers</i>
<i>Management and Organization</i>	6
<i>Business Administration</i>	3
<i>Public Finance</i>	1
<i>Econometrics</i>	1
<i>Economics</i>	1
<i>Political Science and Public Administration</i>	1
<i>Labor Economics and Industrial Relations</i>	1
<i>TOTAL</i>	19

<i>Gender of Participants in the Visiting Lecture</i>	<i>Numbers</i>
<i>Male</i>	11
<i>Female</i>	8
<i>TOTAL</i>	19

Dr. Anne and First Day Participants

A total of 16 participants, including 12 PhD students and 4 researchers attended the visiting lecture on "organisational culture" held on October 5th, 2023. The distribution of participants and PhD students participating in the visiting lecture by departments and gender are as follows:

<i>Participants</i>	<i>Numbers</i>
<i>REMODEL researchers</i>	3
<i>Researcher</i>	1
<i>Departments of PhD Students Participating in the Visiting Lecture</i>	<i>Numbers</i>
<i>Management and Organization</i>	6
<i>Business Administration</i>	3
<i>Public Finance</i>	1
<i>Econometrics</i>	1
<i>Economics</i>	1
<i>TOTAL</i>	16

Gender of Participants in the Visiting Lecture **Numbers**

Male	10
Female	6
TOTAL	16

Dr. Anne and Second Day Participants

On the first day (October 4th, 2023), Dr. Anne together with REMODEL Project Coordinator Prof. Aylin Poroy Arsoy, Project Manager Assoc. Prof. Yasemin Ertan, Communication Manager Assoc. Prof. Elif Yücel, WP Leaders Prof. Nuran Bayram Arlı and Prof. ağan Ta kın, REMODEL researcher Prof. Sevda Gürsakal visited Bursa Uludag University Faculty of Economics and Administrative Sciences Dean Prof. Kadir Yasin Eryiğit in his office. Dean Eryiğit expressed his pleasure with the BMI Laboratory established within our faculty and the studies to be carried out within the scope of the REMODEL project, and thanked to Dr. Anne.

Then, Dr. Anne together with REMODEL Project Coordinator Prof. Aylin Poroy Arsoy, REMODEL managers and WP Leaders visited Bursa Uludag University Rector Prof. Ferudun Yılmaz in his office. Rector Yılmaz Rector Yılmaz stated that he values the Remodel project and expressed that he is proud that such a project in the field of social sciences is carried out within our university and thanked to Dr. Anne for her visit.

2.2.3. Visiting Lecture Evaluation

Visiting lecture evaluation forms were prepared for both participants and the visiting lecturer to evaluate the visiting lecture. At the end of the visiting lecture on both two days, the forms were sent online to the participants and the visiting lecturer. The evaluations of the participants are as follows:

2.2.3.1. Visiting Lecture Evaluation by the Participants

After the first day visiting lecture on "governance, ethics and sustainability", 15 participants evaluated. After the second day visiting lecture on "organisational culture", 14 participants evaluated. The evaluations of the participants are as follows:

Questionnaire	First Day	Second Day
<p>The agenda of the visiting lecture was satisfactory.</p> <p>Strongly agree		
<p>The lecturer was knowledgeable about the visiting lecture topics.</p> <p>Strongly agree		
<p>The lecturer was well prepared.</p> <p>Strongly agree		
<p>The content was well-organised and easy to follow.</p> <p>Strongly agree		
<p>The time allocated for visiting lecture was sufficient.</p> <p>Strongly agree		
<p>The visiting lecture content met my expectations.</p> <p>Strongly agree		
<p>Participation and interaction were encouraged.</p> <p>Strongly agree		

<p>This visiting lecture experience will be useful in my work.</p> <p>Strongly agree		
<p>The venue met all visiting lecture needs.</p> <p>Strongly agree		
<p>I would recommend REMODEL visiting lecture to other people.</p> <p>Strongly agree		
<p>How would you rate the overall organisation of REMODEL visiting lecture (registration, schedule, organisation etc.)</p> <p>Excellent		
<p>How would you rate the visual of the presentations</p> <p>Excellent		
<p>How do you rate the quality of presentations</p> <p>Excellent		

2.2.3.2. Visiting Lecture Evaluation by the Lecturer

After the visiting lectures, here are the evaluations by the visiting lecturer Dr. Anne for both days:

Questionnaire	First Day	Second Day
<p>I had enough time to prepare my presentation.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ●</p> <p>Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>		
<p>The time allowed for the visiting lecture was appropriate.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ●</p> <p>Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>		
<p>The content presented was appropriate to the visiting lecture objectives.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ●</p> <p>Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>		
<p>The content presented was compatible with students' needs.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ●</p> <p>Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>		
<p>The students were interested and enthusiastic.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ●</p> <p>Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>		

<p>I was able to encourage critical thinking and problem-solving.</p> <p>Strongly agree		
<p>The venue met all visiting lecture needs.</p> <p>Strongly agree		
<p>I received positive feedback from faculty members and students after the visiting lecture.</p> <p>Strongly agree		
<p>How do you rate the overall organisation of REMODEL visiting lecture (registration, schedule, communication etc.)</p> <p>Excellent		
<p>How do you rate the overall students' attitudes towards the visiting lecture</p> <p>Excellent		
<p>How do you rate your overall visiting lecture experience</p> <p>Excellent		

2.3. Scope of the Third Staff Exchange (ChatGPT – ULE)

The third REMODEL Visiting Lecture named “Unleashing the power of ChatGPT: Revolutionizing education, research, and management for enhanced productivity” organized by ULE on February 21st, 2024, as part of the staff exchanges conducted for the project. This visiting lecture conducted face-to-face and hosted by the BUU.

2.3.1. Visiting Lecturer and Contents

José Alberto Ben tez Andrades delved into the groundbreaking world of ChatGPT, offering a comprehensive overview of its capabilities and applications in education, research, and management. PhD students explored how ChatGPT can be harnessed as a powerful tool to augment productivity, enhance learning experiences, and streamline research and administrative processes.

**José Alberto Benítez
Andrades**

José Alberto Ben tez Andrades is a computer engineer and PhD in production and computer engineering. He is Associate Professor (tenured) at the Universidad de Leon. He has delivered over 1,500 hours of formal instruction at the university level, encompassing various undergraduate and graduate programs. These include Bachelor's Degrees in Computer Engineering, Industrial and Automatic Electronic Engineering, Industrial Mechanical Engineering, and Master's Degrees in Computer Engineering and Research in Social and Health Sciences. On the pedagogical front, he has completed numerous faculty development courses and has been an active participant in two educational innovation projects, contributing as a team member. He boasts a five-year tenure in teaching. His research primarily focuses on applying

artificial intelligence techniques, knowledge engineering, and social network analysis to address challenges in the healthcare sector. He has authored over 50 publications that are indexed in the Journal Citation Reports (JCR), presented 30 papers at international conferences, and serves as an associate editor for the journals BMC Medical Informatics and Decision Making, as well as PeerJ Computer Science. Additionally, he has been organizing several international conferences since 2018 and acts as a reviewer for international projects funded by the governments of Spain and Peru.

The content of visiting lecture aims to demystify the technology behind ChatGPT, illustrating its potential to transform various professional landscapes.

Through this content, the following learning outcomes were expected:

- Understand the foundational principles and technology behind ChatGPT
- Explore innovative ways to incorporate ChatGPT in teaching methodologies and classroom activities
- Discover how ChatGPT can assist in various stages of research, from literature review to data analysis
- Learn to leverage ChatGPT for effective management and administrative tasks, enhancing efficiency
- Identify best practices for integrating ChatGPT into your workflow to maximize productivity and innovation
- Discuss ethical considerations and limitations of using AI tools like ChatGPT in professional settings

- Engage in practical exercises to experience first-hand the capabilities of ChatGPT
- Develop strategies for staying abreast of evolving AI technologies and their applications in your field

Dr. Alberto talking about "ChatGPT"

2.3.2. Participants

Visiting lectures are open to participation of all PhD students registered in BUU. 15 PhD students attended the visiting lecture on "ChatGPT" held on February 21st, 2024. The distribution of PhD students participating in the visiting lecture by departments and genders are as follows:

<i>Departments of PhD Students Participating in the Visiting Lecture</i>	<i>Numbers</i>
<i>Business Administration</i>	6
<i>Management and Organization</i>	3
<i>Economics</i>	3
<i>Econometrics</i>	1
<i>Private Law</i>	1
<i>Psychology</i>	1
<i>TOTAL</i>	15

<i>Gender of PhD Students Participating in the Visiting Lecture</i>	<i>Numbers</i>
<i>Male</i>	10
<i>Female</i>	5
<i>TOTAL</i>	15

Dr. Alberto and Participants

2.3.3. Visiting Lecture Evaluation

Visiting lecture evaluation forms were prepared for both participants and the visiting lecturer to evaluate the visiting lecture. At the end of the visiting lecture, the forms were sent online to the participants and the visiting lecturer. The evaluations of the participants are as follows:

2.3.3.1. Visiting Lecture Evaluation by the Participants

After the visiting lecture on "ChatGPT", 14 participants evaluated. The evaluations of the participants are as follows:

Questionnaire	
<p>The agenda of the visiting lecture was satisfactory.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ●</p> <p>Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>	
<p>The lecturer was knowledgeable about the visiting lecture topics.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ●</p> <p>Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>	

<p>The lecturer was well prepared.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ● Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Strongly agree</td> <td>71.4%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Agree</td> <td>14.3%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Neutral</td> <td>14.3%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Percentage	Strongly agree	71.4%	Agree	14.3%	Neutral	14.3%
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2.3.3.2. Visiting Lecture Evaluation by the Lecturer

After the visiting lectures, here are the evaluations by the visiting lecturer Dr. Alberto:

<p>Questionnaire</p>					
<p>I had enough time to prepare my presentation.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ● Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Strongly agree</td> <td>100%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Percentage	Strongly agree	100%
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<p>The time allowed for the visiting lecture was appropriate.</p> <p>Strongly agree	
<p>The content presented was appropriate to the visiting lecture objectives.</p> <p>Strongly agree	
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<p>The students were interested and enthusiastic.</p> <p>Strongly agree	
<p>I was able to encourage critical thinking and problem-solving.</p> <p>Strongly agree	
<p>The teaching environment met all visiting lecture needs.</p> <p>Strongly agree	
<p>I received positive feedback from faculty members and students after the visiting lecture.</p> <p>Strongly agree	

<p>How do you rate the overall organisation of REMODEL visiting lecture (registration, schedule, communication etc.)</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ● Satisfaction ●</p> <p>Poor ● Very Poor ●</p>	
<p>How do you rate the overall students' attitudes towards the visiting lecture</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ● Satisfaction ●</p> <p>Poor ● Very Poor ●</p>	
<p>How do you rate your overall visiting lecture experience</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ● Satisfaction ●</p> <p>Poor ● Very Poor ●</p>	

2.4. Scope of the Fourth Staff Exchange (Matlab – ULE)

The fourth REMODEL Visiting Lecture named “MATLAB for validating hypotheses when working with datasets” organized by ULE on February 22nd, 2024, as part of the staff exchanges conducted for the project. This visiting lecture conducted face-to-face and hosted by the BUU.

2.4.1. Visiting Lecturer and Contents

Dr. Hector provided students basic MATLAB knowledge. Thank to this tool the researchers worked with complex datasets in order to develop statistical treatment and machine learning models. PhD students learned the basic primitives understanding the automatic outputs of new AI tools such as ChatGPT.

Héctor Alaiz Moretón

Héctor Alaiz Moretón received his degree in Computer Science, performing the final Project at Dublin Institute of Technology, in 2003. He received his PhD in Information Technologies in 2008 ULE. He has worked as a lecturer since 2005 at the School of Engineering at the ULE. His research interests include knowledge engineering, machine and deep learning, networks communication, and security. He has several works published in international conferences, as well as books, more than 90 scientific publications between JCR papers, Lecture Notes and Scientific Workshops. He has been a member of scientific committees in conferences. He has headed several PhD Thesis and research competitive projects. At present, he is the vice main of RIASC (Institute of Applied Sciences to Cybersecurity).

The content of visiting lecture aims to provide students basic MATLAB knowledge.

Through this content, the following learning outcomes were expected:

- What is MATLAB
- MATLAB Tool for Papers Based on Datasets
- Knowing MATLAB: Mathematical operations, commands scripts, functions, and graphical representation.
- Machine Learning and Statics
- MATLAB with ChatGPT

Dr. Héctor talking about "MATLAB with ChatGPT"

2.4.2. Participants

Visiting lectures are open to participation of all PhD students registered in BUU. 19 PhD students attended the visiting lecture on "MATLAB" held on February 22nd, 2024. The distribution of PhD students participating in the visiting lecture by departments and gender are as follows:

<i>Departments of PhD Students Participating in the Visiting Lecture</i>	<i>Numbers</i>
<i>Business Administration</i>	9
<i>Economics</i>	5
<i>Management and Organization</i>	2
<i>Psychology</i>	2
<i>Econometrics</i>	1
<i>TOTAL</i>	19

<i>Gender of PhD Students Participating in the Visiting Lecture</i>	<i>Numbers</i>
<i>Male</i>	13
<i>Female</i>	6
<i>TOTAL</i>	19

Dr. Héctor and Participants

2.4.3. Visiting Lecture Evaluation

Visiting lecture evaluation forms were prepared for both participants and the visiting lecturer to evaluate the visiting lecture. At the end of the visiting lecture, the forms were sent online to the participants and the visiting lecturer. The evaluations of the participants are as follows:

2.4.3.1. Visiting Lecture Evaluation by the Participants

After the visiting lecture on “Matlab”, 9 participants evaluated. The evaluations of the participants are as follows:

Questionnaire							
<p>The agenda of the visiting lecture was satisfactory.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ●</p> <p>Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>	<table border="1"> <caption>Evaluation Results for Agenda</caption> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Agree</td> <td>66.7%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Strongly agree</td> <td>33.3%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Percentage	Agree	66.7%	Strongly agree	33.3%
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<p>I would recommend REMODEL visiting lecture to other people.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ● Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>	
<p>How would you rate the overall organisation of REMODEL visiting lecture (registration, schedule, organisation etc.)</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ● Satisfaction ● Poor ● Very Poor ●</p>	
<p>How would you rate the visual of the presentations</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ● Satisfaction ● Poor ● Very Poor ●</p>	
<p>How do you rate the quality of presentations</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ● Satisfaction ● Poor ● Very Poor ●</p>	
<p>How would you rate the quality of the visiting lecture</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ● Satisfaction ● Poor ● Very Poor ●</p>	

2.4.3.2. Visiting Lecture Evaluation by the Lecturer

After the visiting lectures, here are the evaluations by the visiting lecturer Dr. Héctor:

<p>Questionnaire</p>	
<p>I had enough time to prepare my presentation.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ● Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>	

<p>The time allowed for the visiting lecture was appropriate.</p> <p>Strongly agree	
<p>The content presented was appropriate to the visiting lecture objectives.</p> <p>Strongly agree	
<p>The content presented was compatible with students' needs.</p> <p>Strongly agree	
<p>The students were interested and enthusiastic.</p> <p>Strongly agree	
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<p>The teaching environment met all visiting lecture needs.</p> <p>Strongly agree	
<p>I received positive feedback from faculty members and students after the visiting lecture.</p> <p>Strongly agree	

<p>How do you rate the overall organisation of REMODEL visiting lecture (registration, schedule, communication etc.)</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ● Satisfaction ●</p> <p>Poor ● Very Poor ●</p>	
<p>How do you rate the overall students' attitudes towards the visiting lecture</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ● Satisfaction ●</p> <p>Poor ● Very Poor ●</p>	
<p>How do you rate your overall visiting lecture experience</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ● Satisfaction ●</p> <p>Poor ● Very Poor ●</p>	

2.5. Scope of the Fifth Staff Exchange (Neuromarketing and Eye-Tracking – ULE)

The fifth REMODEL Visiting Lecture named “Neuromarketing briefing and eye-tracking insights” organized by ULE on May 8th, 2024, as part of the staff exchanges conducted for the project. This visiting lecture conducted face-to-face and hosted by the BUU.

2.5.1. Visiting Lecturer and Contents

Aroa conducted a neuromarketing briefing to undertake projects with local companies in the hospitality and tourism sector. PhD students understood the importance of incorporating information about the sample, technologies, client profile, fieldwork organization, and experimental protocol outlined in the briefing for successful project execution. Additionally, a practical case study has been conducted using an online eye-tracking software to provide a first approach to eye-tracking analysis.

Aroa Costa-Feito

Aroa Costa-Feito is an Assistant Professor of Marketing at the Faculty of Economics and Business Sciences of the ULE. She is also a PhD Candidate in Consumer Neuroscience and Neuromarketing, holding a Master of Research in Business Economics and a Master's degree in International Tourism Management. In addition to her active involvement in European projects, conferences, and scientific publications, her teaching primarily focuses on tourist marketing, experimental market research techniques (neuromarketing), and consumer behaviour. Moreover, she has 10 years of experience working as a Marketing Director for various companies such as AMR Collection, in the tourism sector, CRAS Dance and Por Alegría, in the sports sector. She has also worked in the Marketing

Department of the multinational TUI within the tourism sector, and Sociograph Neuromarketing as a research consultant.

The content of visiting lecture aims to explore how to conduct a neuromarketing briefing to undertake projects with local companies in the hospitality and tourism sector.

Through this content, the following learning outcomes were expected:

- Understanding the key sections that a neuromarketing briefing should include for effective project management with companies.
- Understanding the concept of eye-tracking and what it measures.
- Being able to conduct an online eye-tracking study and draw relevant conclusions leading to business implications.

Aroa Costa-Feito talking about "Neuromarketing"

2.5.2. Participants

Visiting lectures are open to participation of all PhD students and early-stage researchers registered in BUU. 35 PhD students and early-stage researchers attended the visiting lecture on "Neuromarketing" held on May 8th, 2024. The distribution of early-stage researchers and PhD students participating in the visiting lecture by departments and gender are as follows:

Participants	Numbers
<i>Early-stage researchers</i>	24
Departments of PhD Students Participating in the Visiting Lecture	Numbers
<i>Business Administration</i>	6
<i>Economics</i>	2
<i>Physical education and sports</i>	2
<i>Econometrics</i>	1
TOTAL	35
<hr/>	
Gender of Participants in the Visiting Lecture	Numbers
<i>Male</i>	20
<i>Female</i>	15
TOTAL	35

Aroa Costa-Feito and Participants

2.5.3. Visiting Lecture Evaluation

Visiting lecture evaluation forms were prepared for both participants and the visiting lecturer to evaluate the visiting lecture. At the end of the visiting lecture, the forms were sent online to the participants and the visiting lecturer. The evaluations of the participants are as follows:

2.5.3.1. Visiting Lecture Evaluation by the Participants

After the visiting lecture on “Neuromarketing briefing and eye-tracking insights”, 7 participants evaluated. The evaluations of the participants are as follows:

Questionnaire							
<p>The agenda of the visiting lecture was satisfactory.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ●</p> <p>Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>	<table border="1" data-bbox="1023 1406 1249 1630"> <tr><th>Response</th><th>Percentage</th></tr> <tr><td>Agree</td><td>71.4%</td></tr> <tr><td>Strongly agree</td><td>28.6%</td></tr> </table>	Response	Percentage	Agree	71.4%	Strongly agree	28.6%
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<p>I would recommend REMODEL visiting lecture to other people.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ● Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>	
<p>How would you rate the overall organisation of REMODEL visiting lecture (registration, schedule, organisation etc.)</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ● Satisfaction ● Poor ● Very Poor ●</p>	
<p>How would you rate the visual of the presentations</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ● Satisfaction ● Poor ● Very Poor ●</p>	
<p>How do you rate the quality of presentations</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ● Satisfaction ● Poor ● Very Poor ●</p>	
<p>How would you rate the quality of the visiting lecture</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ● Satisfaction ● Poor ● Very Poor ●</p>	

2.5.3.2. Visiting Lecture Evaluation by the Lecturer

After the visiting lectures, here are the evaluations by the visiting lecturer Aroa:

Questionnaire	
<p>I had enough time to prepare my presentation.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ● Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>	

<p>The time allowed for the visiting lecture was appropriate.</p> <p>Strongly agree	
<p>The content presented was appropriate to the visiting lecture objectives.</p> <p>Strongly agree	
<p>The content presented was compatible with students' needs.</p> <p>Strongly agree	
<p>The students were interested and enthusiastic.</p> <p>Strongly agree	
<p>I was able to encourage critical thinking and problem-solving.</p> <p>Strongly agree	
<p>The teaching environment met all visiting lecture needs.</p> <p>Strongly agree	
<p>I received positive feedback from faculty members and students after the visiting lecture.</p> <p>Strongly agree	

<p>How do you rate the overall organisation of REMODEL visiting lecture (registration, schedule, communication etc.)</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ● Satisfaction ●</p> <p>Poor ● Very Poor ●</p>	
<p>How do you rate the overall students' attitudes towards the visiting lecture</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ● Satisfaction ●</p> <p>Poor ● Very Poor ●</p>	
<p>How do you rate your overall visiting lecture experience</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ● Satisfaction ●</p> <p>Poor ● Very Poor ●</p>	

2.6. Scope of the Sixth Staff Exchange (Web Scraping – ULE)

The sixth REMODEL Visiting Lecture named “Web scraping fundamentals for structured data” organized by ULE on May 9th, 2024, as part of the staff exchanges conducted for the project. This visiting lecture conducted face-to-face and hosted by the BUU.

2.6.1. Visiting Lecturer and Contents

Sofia transferred about the web scraping data download technique, as well as PhD students explored the main tools that allow data downloading on websites.

Sofía Blanco-Moreno

Sofía Blanco-Moreno is a Marketing and Tourism expert with a specialization in Digital Marketing and technologies such as Web Scraping and Artificial Intelligence (Machine Learning and Deep Learning) applied in Tourism and Hospitality. She is also a PhD student and an assistant professor at the ULE, and she has worked as a Digital Marketing expert on international companies such as Meliá Hotels. She has received several research awards, such as the best communication at the AIRSI and AIM 2023 conferences, I UAM-ASSECO Business Case Award 2022 and "Proof of concept" within the University-Business Knowledge Transfer Plan for the platform Photo Data Tour Analytics.

Regarding her professional training, she has taught web scraping and artificial intelligence analysis courses at different universities such as Lleida, Zaragoza, Valencia and Valladolid, as well as in the REDINTUR network and the European university EURECA.

The content of visiting lecture aims to learn about the web scraping data download technique, as well as explore the main tools that allow data downloading on websites. At the end of the lecture, PhD students download data from websites related to sustainability and tourism, and create databases to apply in their own research areas.

Through this content, the following learning outcomes were expected:

- Understand what web scraping is, and differentiate between web crawler and web scraper.
- To know the main free and paid tools for web scraping.
- How to download data from tourist platforms like Tripadvisor.
- How to download data from social media platforms like Instagram or Twitter.

Sofia Blanco-Moreno talking about "Web scraping data"

2.6.2. Participants

Visiting lectures are open to participation of all PhD students and early-stage researchers registered in BUU. 27 PhD students and early-stage researchers attended the visiting lecture on "Web scraping fundamentals for structured data" held on May 9th, 2024. The distribution of early-stage researchers and PhD students participating in the visiting lecture by departments and gender are as follows:

<i>Participants</i>	<i>Numbers</i>
<i>Early-stage researchers</i>	20
<i>Departments of PhD Students Participating in the Visiting Lecture</i>	<i>Numbers</i>
<i>Business Administration</i>	3
<i>Economics</i>	1
<i>Physical education and sports</i>	1
<i>Econometrics</i>	1
<i>Psychology</i>	1
<i>TOTAL</i>	<i>27</i>
<i>Gender of Participants in the Visiting Lecture</i>	<i>Numbers</i>
<i>Male</i>	15
<i>Female</i>	12
<i>TOTAL</i>	<i>27</i>

Sofía Blanco-Moreno and Participants

2.6.3. Visiting Lecture Evaluation

Visiting lecture evaluation forms were prepared for both participants and the visiting lecturer to evaluate the visiting lecture. At the end of the visiting lecture, the forms were sent online to the participants and the visiting lecturer. The evaluations of the participants are as follows:

2.6.3.1. Visiting Lecture Evaluation by the Participants

After the visiting lecture on "Web scraping fundamentals for structured data", 5 participants evaluated. The evaluations of the participants are as follows:

Questionnaire							
<p>The agenda of the visiting lecture was satisfactory.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ●</p> <p>Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>	<table border="1"> <caption>Data for Agenda Satisfactory</caption> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Agree</td> <td>80%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Strongly agree</td> <td>20%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Percentage	Agree	80%	Strongly agree	20%
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<p>The lecturer was knowledgeable about the visiting lecture topics.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ●</p> <p>Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>	<table border="1"> <caption>Data for Lecturer Knowledgeable</caption> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Strongly agree</td> <td>60%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Agree</td> <td>40%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Percentage	Strongly agree	60%	Agree	40%
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<p>The lecturer was well prepared.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ● Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Strongly agree</td> <td>60%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Agree</td> <td>40%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Percentage	Strongly agree	60%	Agree	40%		
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<p>I would recommend REMODEL visiting lecture to other people.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ● Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>	
<p>How would you rate the overall organisation of REMODEL visiting lecture (registration, schedule, organisation etc.)</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ● Satisfaction ● Poor ● Very Poor ●</p>	
<p>How would you rate the visual of the presentations</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ● Satisfaction ● Poor ● Very Poor ●</p>	
<p>How do you rate the quality of presentations</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ● Satisfaction ● Poor ● Very Poor ●</p>	
<p>How would you rate the quality of the visiting lecture</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ● Satisfaction ● Poor ● Very Poor ●</p>	

2.6.3.2. Visiting Lecture Evaluation by the Lecturer

After the visiting lectures, here are the evaluations by the visiting lecturer Sofia:

<p>Questionnaire</p>	
<p>I had enough time to prepare my presentation.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ● Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>	

<p>The time allowed for the visiting lecture was appropriate.</p> <p>Strongly agree	
<p>The content presented was appropriate to the visiting lecture objectives.</p> <p>Strongly agree	
<p>The content presented was compatible with students' needs.</p> <p>Strongly agree	
<p>The students were interested and enthusiastic.</p> <p>Strongly agree	
<p>I was able to encourage critical thinking and problem-solving.</p> <p>Strongly agree	
<p>The teaching environment met all visiting lecture needs.</p> <p>Strongly agree	
<p>I received positive feedback from faculty members and students after the visiting lecture.</p> <p>Strongly agree	

<p>How do you rate the overall organisation of REMODEL visiting lecture (registration, schedule, communication etc.)</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ● Satisfaction ●</p> <p>Poor ● Very Poor ●</p>	
<p>How do you rate the overall students' attitudes towards the visiting lecture</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ● Satisfaction ●</p> <p>Poor ● Very Poor ●</p>	
<p>How do you rate your overall visiting lecture experience</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ● Satisfaction ●</p> <p>Poor ● Very Poor ●</p>	

2.7. Scope of the Seventh Staff Exchange (Creative entrepreneurship – ATU)

The seventh REMODEL Visiting Lecture named “Creative entrepreneurship – exploring lived experience” organized by ATU on May 15th, 2024, as part of the staff exchanges conducted for the project. This visiting lecture conducted face-to-face and hosted by the BUU.

2.7.1. Visiting Lecturer and Contents

Tena’s delivery explored the topic of creative entrepreneurship. She focused on qualitative research. PhD students discussed the lived experience of creative entrepreneurs and gained insights into the methods used to surface such experience.

Tena Patten

Dr. Tena Patten currently teaches in the Department of Design and Creative Media, based in the School of Business at ATU. She is also the Joint Course Director of the ATU Doctorate in Business Administration.

Tena’s teaching interests straddle the areas of creativity, business, entrepreneurship and education. Tena has a keen interest in learning by doing, and frequently employs the Action Learning methodology in her teaching practice. Additionally, Tena was involved in the co-creation of a Design Thinking methodology called UNIQUE, and she has deployed training in this technique in collaborative projects involving public sector stakeholder partners, secondary school

educators and social enterprises. Tena completed her doctoral studies at Northumbria University in 2017. Her research centred on examining the lived experience of entrepreneurs in the creative industries. Previously she attained MBA

and MA (French and Music) awards at Trinity College Dublin. Prior to commencing lecturing in 2003, she worked in a range of industry settings internationally, and she brings a wealth of industry insight and connections to her pedagogical practice.

The content of visiting lecture aims to learn about the creative entrepreneurship. Through this content, the following learning outcomes were expected:

- Explore theoretical and practical issues relating to entrepreneurial opportunity
- Identify the characteristics of creative industry entrepreneurs
- Discuss the benefits and challenges of conducting qualitative research
- Critique the use of interviews as a data collection method.

Dr. Tena Patten talking about "Creative entrepreneurship"

2.7.2. Participants

Visiting lectures are open to participation of all PhD students and early-stage researchers registered in BUU. 27 PhD students and early-stage researchers attended the visiting lecture on "Creative entrepreneurship – exploring lived experience" held on May 15th, 2024. The distribution of early-stage researchers and PhD students participating in the visiting lecture by departments and gender are as follows:

<i>Participants</i>	<i>Numbers</i>
<i>Early-stage researchers</i>	21
<i>Departments of PhD Students Participating in the Visiting Lecture</i>	<i>Numbers</i>
<i>Business Administration</i>	4
<i>Physical education and sports</i>	1
<i>Econometrics</i>	1
<i>TOTAL</i>	<i>27</i>
<i>Gender of Participants in the Visiting Lecture</i>	<i>Numbers</i>
<i>Male</i>	17
<i>Female</i>	10
<i>TOTAL</i>	<i>27</i>

Dr. Tena and Participants

2.7.3. Visiting Lecture Evaluation

Visiting lecture evaluation forms were prepared for both participants and the visiting lecturer to evaluate the visiting lecture. At the end of the visiting lecture, the forms were sent online to the participants and the visiting lecturer. The evaluations of the participants are as follows:

2.7.3.1. Visiting Lecture Evaluation by the Participants

After the visiting lecture on "Creative entrepreneurship – exploring lived experience", 22 participants evaluated. The evaluations of the participants are as follows:

Questionnaire									
<p>The agenda of the visiting lecture was satisfactory.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ● Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>	<table border="1"> <caption>Data for 'The agenda of the visiting lecture was satisfactory.'</caption> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Strongly agree</td> <td>59.1%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Agree</td> <td>31.8%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Neutral</td> <td>9.1%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Percentage	Strongly agree	59.1%	Agree	31.8%	Neutral	9.1%
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<p>Participation and interaction were encouraged.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ●</p> <p>Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Strongly agree</td> <td>59.1%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Agree</td> <td>31.8%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Neutral</td> <td>9.1%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Disagree</td> <td>0%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Strongly disagree</td> <td>0%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Percentage	Strongly agree	59.1%	Agree	31.8%	Neutral	9.1%	Disagree	0%	Strongly disagree	0%
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<p>I would recommend REMODEL visiting lecture to other people.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ● Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>	
<p>How would you rate the overall organisation of REMODEL visiting lecture (registration, schedule, organisation etc.)</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ● Satisfaction ● Poor ● Very Poor ●</p>	
<p>How would you rate the visual of the presentations</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ● Satisfaction ● Poor ● Very Poor ●</p>	
<p>How do you rate the quality of presentations</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ● Satisfaction ● Poor ● Very Poor ●</p>	
<p>How would you rate the quality of the visiting lecture</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ● Satisfaction ● Poor ● Very Poor ●</p>	

2.7.3.2. Visiting Lecture Evaluation by the Lecturer

After the visiting lectures, here are the evaluations by the visiting lecturer Dr. Tena:

<p>Questionnaire</p>	
<p>I had enough time to prepare my presentation.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ● Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>	

<p>The time allowed for the visiting lecture was appropriate.</p> <p>Strongly agree	
<p>The content presented was appropriate to the visiting lecture objectives.</p> <p>Strongly agree	
<p>The content presented was compatible with students' needs.</p> <p>Strongly agree	
<p>The students were interested and enthusiastic.</p> <p>Strongly agree	
<p>I was able to encourage critical thinking and problem-solving.</p> <p>Strongly agree	
<p>The teaching environment met all visiting lecture needs.</p> <p>Strongly agree	
<p>I received positive feedback from faculty members and students after the visiting lecture.</p> <p>Strongly agree	

<p>How do you rate the overall organisation of REMODEL visiting lecture (registration, schedule, communication etc.)</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ● Satisfaction ●</p> <p>Poor ● Very Poor ●</p>	
<p>How do you rate the overall students' attitudes towards the visiting lecture</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ● Satisfaction ●</p> <p>Poor ● Very Poor ●</p>	
<p>How do you rate your overall visiting lecture experience</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ● Satisfaction ●</p> <p>Poor ● Very Poor ●</p>	

2.8. Scope of the Eighth Staff Exchange (Designing and Conducting Quantitative Research – ATU)

The eight REMODEL Visiting Lecture named “Designing and Conducting Quantitative Research” organized by ATU on November 7-8th, 2024, as part of the staff exchanges conducted for the project. This visiting lecture conducted face-to-face and hosted by the BUU.

2.8.1. Visiting Lecturer and Contents

George explained that how to develop a conceptual framework with an appropriate research protocol, design appropriate surveys, and implement effective measurement techniques.

George Onofrei

George Onofrei is Senior Lecturer in Operations and Supply Chain Management, at ATU, Ireland. He has completed his PhD at UCD Smurfit Graduate Business School, Ireland in the area of Operations and Supply Chain Management. He served on the Board of the European Operations Management Association (EurOMA) and was the Vice-President of Global Manufacturing Research Group (GMRG). His research interests focus on supply chain practices, sustainability, business data analytics and behavioural operations in manufacturing and service industries. His work has appeared in premier journals including International Journal of Production and Operations Management, Journal of Business Research, Business Strategy and the

Environment, Supply Chain Management: An International Journal, Production Planning and Control, Resource Conservation and Recycling, International Journal of Production Research, Total Quality Management and Business Excellence, Operations Management Research and many more. He is a recipient of Lean Business Ireland Award (2019) for the Best Contribution to Lean/Operational.

In this visiting lecture, participants covered the fundamental principles of quantitative research, including some introduction to statistical analysis. Additionally, they covered measurement concepts, including reliability and validity, and how to assess and improve the quality of data.

Through this content, the following learning outcomes were expected:

- Develop a conceptual framework with an appropriate research protocol
- Explore the different options for quantitative research methods
- Understand the challenges in quantitative research design
- Explain the concepts of reliability and validity

Dr. George Onofrei talking about "Quantitative Research Methods"

2.8.2. Participants

Visiting lecture is open to participation of all PhD students and early-stage researchers registered in BUU. 31 PhD students and early-stage researchers attended the visiting lecture on "Designing and conducting quantitative research" held on November 7-8th, 2024. The distribution of early-stage researchers and PhD students participating in the visiting lecture by departments and gender are as follows:

Participants		Numbers
<i>Early-stage researchers</i>		23
Departments of PhD students participating in the visiting lecture		
<i>English Language and Literature</i>		2
<i>Biotechnology</i>		1
<i>Econometrics</i>		1
<i>Marketing</i>		1
<i>Psychology</i>		1
<i>Psychological Counselling and Guidance</i>		1
<i>Textile Engineering</i>		1
TOTAL		31
Gender of Participants in the Visiting Lecture		Numbers
<i>Male</i>		11
<i>Female</i>		20
TOTAL		31

Dr. Onofrei and Participants

2.8.3. Visiting Lecture Evaluation

Visiting lecture evaluation forms were prepared for both participants and the visiting lecturer to evaluate the visiting lecture. At the end of the visiting lecture, the forms were sent online to the participants and the visiting lecturer.

2.8.3.1. Visiting Lecture Evaluation by the Participants

After the visiting lecture on "Designing and conducting quantitative research", 16 participants evaluated. The evaluations of the participants are as follows:

Questionnaire	
<p>The agenda of the visiting lecture was satisfactory.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ● Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>	
<p>The lecturer was knowledgeable about the visiting lecture topics.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ● Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>	

<p>The lecturer was well prepared.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ● Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Strongly agree</td> <td>75%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Agree</td> <td>25%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Percentage	Strongly agree	75%	Agree	25%		
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<p>The content was well-organised and easy to follow.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ● Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Strongly agree</td> <td>75%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Agree</td> <td>25%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Percentage	Strongly agree	75%	Agree	25%		
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<p>The visiting lecture content met my expectations.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ● Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Strongly agree</td> <td>62.5%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Agree</td> <td>25%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Neutral</td> <td>12.5%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Percentage	Strongly agree	62.5%	Agree	25%	Neutral	12.5%
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<p>I would recommend REMODEL visiting lecture to other people.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ● Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>	<table border="1"> <tr><th>Response</th><th>Percentage</th></tr> <tr><td>Strongly agree</td><td>68.8%</td></tr> <tr><td>Agree</td><td>25%</td></tr> <tr><td>Neutral</td><td>6.2%</td></tr> </table>	Response	Percentage	Strongly agree	68.8%	Agree	25%	Neutral	6.2%
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<p>How would you rate the overall organisation of REMODEL visiting lecture (registration, schedule, organisation etc.)</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ● Satisfaction ● Poor ● Very Poor ●</p>	<table border="1"> <tr><th>Response</th><th>Percentage</th></tr> <tr><td>Excellent</td><td>50%</td></tr> <tr><td>Good</td><td>50%</td></tr> </table>	Response	Percentage	Excellent	50%	Good	50%		
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Response	Percentage								
Excellent	75%								
Good	25%								

2.7.3.2. Visiting Lecture Evaluation by the Lecturer

After the visiting lectures, here are the evaluations by the visiting lecturer Dr. Onofrei:

<p>Questionnaire</p>					
<p>I had enough time to prepare my presentation.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ● Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>	<table border="1"> <tr><th>Response</th><th>Percentage</th></tr> <tr><td>Strongly agree</td><td>100%</td></tr> </table>	Response	Percentage	Strongly agree	100%
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<p>The time allowed for the visiting lecture was appropriate.</p> <p>Strongly agree	
<p>The content presented was appropriate to the visiting lecture objectives.</p> <p>Strongly agree	
<p>The content presented was compatible with students' needs.</p> <p>Strongly agree	
<p>The students were interested and enthusiastic.</p> <p>Strongly agree	
<p>I was able to encourage critical thinking and problem-solving.</p> <p>Strongly agree	
<p>The teaching environment met all visiting lecture needs.</p> <p>Strongly agree	
<p>I received positive feedback from faculty members and students after the visiting lecture.</p> <p>Strongly agree	

<p>How do you rate the overall organisation of REMODEL visiting lecture (registration, schedule, communication etc.)</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ● Satisfaction ●</p> <p>Poor ● Very Poor ●</p>	
<p>How do you rate the overall students' attitudes towards the visiting lecture</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ● Satisfaction ●</p> <p>Poor ● Very Poor ●</p>	
<p>How do you rate your overall visiting lecture experience</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ● Satisfaction ●</p> <p>Poor ● Very Poor ●</p>	

2.9. Scope of the Ninth Staff Exchange (AI powered insights – ULE)

The ninth REMODEL Visiting Lecture named “AI powered insights: Analyzing visual and textual content on social media for destination marketing management” organized by ULE on March 19th, 2025 and it was held online.

2.9.1. Visiting Lecturer and Contents

In this event, Sofia provided participants with information on how artificial intelligence, machine learning, and deep learning techniques can be used to analyze user-generated content from social media platforms.

Sofía Blanco-Moreno

Sofía Blanco-Moreno is a Marketing and Tourism expert with a specialization in Digital Marketing and technologies such as Web Scraping and Artificial Intelligence (Machine Learning and Deep Learning) applied in Tourism and Hospitality. She is also an assistant professor at the ULE, and she has worked as a Digital Marketing expert on international companies such as Meliá Hotels. She has received several research awards, such as the best communication at the AIRSI and AIM 2023 conferences, I UAM-ASSECO Business Case Award 2022 and "Proof of concept" within the University-Business Knowledge Transfer Plan for the platform Photo Data Tour Analytics. Regarding her professional training, she has taught web scraping and

artificial intelligence analysis courses at different universities such as Lleida, Zaragoza, Valencia and Valladolid, as well as in the REDINTUR network and the European university EURECA.

Within the scope of this workshop, particular emphasis was placed on how textual content, visual content, and metadata are processed to derive insights into tourist behavior, engagement patterns, and the attractiveness of destinations. Participants developed an understanding of how AI-powered methodologies can leverage social media content to advance destination marketing strategies. Through this content, the following learning outcomes were expected:

- Understand the role of AI in analyzing social media content for tourism research.
- Identify key data sources and extraction techniques, including web scraping.
- Explain how text analysis, image recognition, and metadata analysis contribute to destination marketing strategies.
- Recognize ethical considerations and best practices in handling social media data.

Sofia talking about "Analyzing visual and textual content on social media with AI-powered methodologies"

2.9.2. Participants

Visiting lecture is open to participation of all PhD students and early-stage researchers registered in Bursa Uludag University. 29 PhD students and early-stage researchers attended the visiting lecture on "AI powered insights: Analyzing visual and textual content on social media for destination marketing management" held on March 19th, 2025. The distribution of early-stage researchers and PhD students participating in the visiting lecture by departments and gender are as follows:

<i>Participants</i>		<i>Numbers</i>
<i>Early-stage researchers</i>		23
<i>Departments of PhD students participating in the visiting lecture</i>	Numbers	
<i>Business Administration</i>		6
TOTAL		29

□

<i>Gender of Participants in the Visiting Lecture</i>		<i>Numbers</i>
<i>Male</i>		15
<i>Female</i>		24
TOTAL		29

□

2.9.3. Visiting Lecture Evaluation

Visiting lecture evaluation forms were prepared for both participants and the visiting lecturer to evaluate the visiting lecture. At the end of the visiting lecture, the forms were sent online to the participants and the visiting lecturer.

2.9.3.1. Visiting Lecture Evaluation by the Participants

After the visiting lecture on "AI powered insights: Analyzing visual and textual content on social media for destination marketing management", 7 participants evaluated. The evaluations of the participants are as follows:

Questionnaire									
<p>The agenda of the visiting lecture was satisfactory.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ●</p> <p>Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>	<table border="1"> <caption>Evaluation Results for Agenda Satisfactoriness</caption> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Strongly agree</td> <td>57.1%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Agree</td> <td>28.6%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Neutral</td> <td>14.3%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Percentage	Strongly agree	57.1%	Agree	28.6%	Neutral	14.3%
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<p>The online learning environment met all visiting lecture needs.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ● Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Agree</td> <td>57.1%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Strongly agree</td> <td>14.3%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Disagree</td> <td>14.3%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Neutral</td> <td>14.3%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Percentage	Agree	57.1%	Strongly agree	14.3%	Disagree	14.3%	Neutral	14.3%
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<p>I would recommend REMODEL visiting lecture to other people.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ● Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>	
<p>How would you rate the overall organisation of REMODEL visiting lecture (registration, schedule, organisation etc.)</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ● Satisfaction ● Poor ● Very Poor ●</p>	
<p>How would you rate the visual of the presentations</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ● Satisfaction ● Poor ● Very Poor ●</p>	
<p>How do you rate the quality of presentations</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ● Satisfaction ● Poor ● Very Poor ●</p>	
<p>How would you rate the quality of the visiting lecture</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ● Satisfaction ● Poor ● Very Poor ●</p>	

2.9.3.2. Visiting Lecture Evaluation by the Lecturer

After the visiting lectures, here are the evaluations by the visiting lecturer Dr. Sofia Blanco-Moreno

Questionnaire	
<p>I had enough time to prepare my presentation.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ● Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>	

<p>The time allowed for the visiting lecture was appropriate.</p> <p>Strongly agree	
<p>The content presented was appropriate to the visiting lecture objectives.</p> <p>Strongly agree	
<p>The content presented was compatible with students' needs.</p> <p>Strongly agree	
<p>The students were interested and enthusiastic.</p> <p>Strongly agree	
<p>I was able to encourage critical thinking and problem-solving.</p> <p>Strongly agree	
<p>The teaching environment met all visiting lecture needs.</p> <p>Strongly agree	
<p>I received positive feedback from faculty members and students after the visiting lecture.</p> <p>Strongly agree	

<p>How do you rate the overall organisation of REMODEL visiting lecture (registration, schedule, communication etc.)</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ● Satisfaction ●</p> <p>Poor ● Very Poor ●</p>	
<p>How do you rate the overall students' attitudes towards the visiting lecture</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ● Satisfaction ●</p> <p>Poor ● Very Poor ●</p>	
<p>How do you rate your overall visiting lecture experience</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ● Satisfaction ●</p> <p>Poor ● Very Poor ●</p>	

2.10. Scope of the Tenth Staff Exchange (A neuroscientific perspective in destination marketing – ULE)

The tenth REMODEL Visiting Lecture named “Nature or city A neuroscientific perspective on emotion, cognition, and personality in destination marketing” organized by ULE on March 20th, 2025 and it was held online.

2.10.1. Visiting Lecturer and Contents

Aroa presented two consumer neuroscience studies applied to tourism marketing: one focusing on a nature-based destination (Australia) and the other on an urban destination (New York).

Aroa Costa-Feito

Dr. Aroa Costa-Feito is an assistant professor and researcher at the ULE, specializing in consumer neuroscience, with a particular focus on the tourism industry and behavioural change for biodiversity conservation. Her research employs advanced neurophysiological tools, including eye-tracking, electroencephalography (EEG), and galvanic skin response (GSR), to analyse consumer behaviour and its impact on decision-making processes. Currently, she is actively involvement in several European projects, focusing on the practical application of scientific knowledge to generate a meaningful impact. She is an active member of the Society for Conservation Biology (Conservation Marketing group), the World Wildlife

Fund (WWF), and the Spanish Marketing Association (AEMARK), aiming to promote behavioural change for biodiversity conservation.

In this visiting lecture, the influence of conscious and non-conscious responses – such as emotional impact, specific emotions, attention, and memory – towards promotional destination spots on tourists' travel intentions and decision-making processes was examined. In addition, the role of individual personality traits in shaping emotional responses and visual attention patterns was evaluated. Through this content, the following learning outcomes were expected:

- Understand the impact of consumer neuroscience in tourism marketing.
- Identify the role of personality in emotional and visual responses.
- Apply practical insights to tourism promotion strategies.

Aroa talking about "Neuroscientific perspective on emotion, cognition, and personality in destination marketing"

2.10.2. Participants

Visiting lecture is open to participation of all PhD students and early-stage researchers registered in Bursa Uludag University. 25 PhD students and early-stage researchers attended the visiting lecture on "Nature or city? A neuroscientific perspective on emotion, cognition, and personality in destination marketing" held on March 20th, 2025. The distribution of early-stage researchers and PhD students participating in the visiting lecture by departments and gender are as follows:

		<i>Participants</i>	<i>Numbers</i>
		<i>Early-stage researchers</i>	21
<i>Departments of PhD students participating in the visiting lecture</i>		Numbers	
		<i>Business Administration</i>	3
		<i>Economics</i>	1
		TOTAL	25

		<i>Gender of Participants in the Visiting Lecture</i>	<i>Numbers</i>
		<i>Male</i>	13
		<i>Female</i>	22
		TOTAL	25

2.10.3. Visiting Lecture Evaluation

Visiting lecture evaluation forms were prepared for both participants and the visiting lecturer to evaluate the visiting lecture. At the end of the visiting lecture, the forms were sent online to the participants and the visiting lecturer.

2.10.3.1. Visiting Lecture Evaluation by the Participants

After the visiting lecture on "Nature or city? A neuroscientific perspective on emotion, cognition, and personality in destination marketing", 10 participants evaluated. The evaluations of the participants are as follows:

Questionnaire	
<p>The agenda of the visiting lecture was satisfactory.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ● Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>	
<p>The lecturer was knowledgeable about the visiting lecture topics.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ● Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>	

<p>The lecturer was well prepared.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ● Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Strongly agree</td> <td>70%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Agree</td> <td>20%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Neutral</td> <td>10%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Disagree</td> <td>0%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Strongly disagree</td> <td>0%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Percentage	Strongly agree	70%	Agree	20%	Neutral	10%	Disagree	0%	Strongly disagree	0%
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2.10.3.2. Visiting Lecture Evaluation by the Lecturer

After the visiting lectures, here are the evaluations by the visiting lecturer Dr. Aroa Costa-Feito

Questionnaire					
<p>I had enough time to prepare my presentation.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ● Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>	<table border="1"> <tr><th>Response</th><th>Percentage</th></tr> <tr><td>Strongly agree</td><td>100%</td></tr> </table>	Response	Percentage	Strongly agree	100%
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<p>The time allowed for the visiting lecture was appropriate.</p> <p>Strongly agree	
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<p>The teaching environment met all visiting lecture needs.</p> <p>Strongly agree	
<p>I received positive feedback from faculty members and students after the visiting lecture.</p> <p>Strongly agree	

<p>How do you rate the overall organisation of REMODEL visiting lecture (registration, schedule, communication etc.)</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ● Satisfaction ●</p> <p>Poor ● Very Poor ●</p>	
<p>How do you rate the overall students' attitudes towards the visiting lecture</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ● Satisfaction ●</p> <p>Poor ● Very Poor ●</p>	
<p>How do you rate your overall visiting lecture experience</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ● Satisfaction ●</p> <p>Poor ● Very Poor ●</p>	

2.11. Scope of the Eleventh Staff Exchange (Beyond Green: Exploring Sustainability's Deep Dimensions – ATU)

The eleventh REMODEL Visiting Lecture named “Beyond Green: Exploring Sustainability’s Deep Dimensions – Theory, Praxis and Navigating the Complexities for a Resilient Future” organized by ATU on May 27th, 2025 at BUU FEAS.

2.11.1. Visiting Lecturer and Contents

Ciaran has addressed sustainability at an advanced level, examining complex socio-ecological systems through theoretical frameworks and critical analyses.

Ciarán Ó’hannracháin

Dr. Ciarán Ó’hannracháin is a Faculty of Business Strategic Projects Manager at ATU with a focus on Research & Collaboration Projects and holds the Operational Board Chair of the World Technology Universities Network (WTUN), a global network of universities focused on delivering on the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Previous roles include Project Manager of Academic Planning and Strategy, Internationalisation and External Engagement during the creation of ATU. Ciarán has also held Senior Academic Management positions in the Irish, UK, US and Swiss education systems, and lectures in Hospitality and Tourism Management. His research interests include both Education (Global HE Policy and Internationalisation of HE) and Business (Sustainable Regional Development, Business Model Innovation, Talent Management and Staff Training and Development).

In this visiting lecture event, participants engaged with the latest research, emerging technologies, and innovative governance approaches, and examined the behavioural and systemic dimensions of sustainability transitions through case studies. Aiming to sharpen analytical tools and inspire impactful research, the session fostered discussion of new questions and deepened commitment to the sustainability agenda.

Through this content, the following learning outcomes were expected:

- Critically evaluate key theoretical frameworks in sustainability science, assessing their strengths, limitations, and real-world relevance.
- Analyse cutting-edge research and frontier challenges, focusing on emerging technologies, governance models, and behavioural dynamics in sustainability transitions.
- Apply multi-dimensional perspectives to case studies, integrating environmental, social, and economic factors to propose evidence-based solutions.
- Formulate impactful research questions that address knowledge gaps and demonstrate doctoral-level readiness to advance the sustainability field.

Dr. Ciarán Ó'hannracháin is talking about Ú•caí

2.11.2. Participants

Visiting lecture is open to participation of all PhD students and early-stage researchers registered in BUU. 31 PhD students and early-stage researchers attended the visiting lecture on "Designing and conducting quantitative research" held on November 7-8th, 2024. The distribution of early-stage researchers and PhD students participating in the visiting lecture by departments and gender are as follows:

	Participants	Numbers
Departments of PhD students participating in the visiting lecture	<i>Early-stage researchers</i>	46
	<i>Business Administration</i>	2
	TOTAL	48
Gender of Participants in the Visiting Lecture		
	<i>Male</i>	29
	<i>Female</i>	19
	TOTAL	48

Dr. Ó'hannracháin and Participants

2.11.3. Visiting Lecture Evaluation

Visiting lecture evaluation forms were prepared for both participants and the visiting lecturer to evaluate the visiting lecture. At the end of the visiting lecture, the forms were sent online to the participants and the visiting lecturer.

2.11.3.1. Visiting Lecture Evaluation by the Participants

After the visiting lecture on "Beyond Green: Exploring Sustainability's Deep Dimensions – Theory, Praxis and Navigating the Complexities for a Resilient Future", 12 participants evaluated. The evaluations of the participants are as follows:

Questionnaire							
<p>The agenda of the visiting lecture was satisfactory.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ● Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>	<table border="1"> <caption>Agenda Evaluation Data</caption> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Strongly agree</td> <td>83.3%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Agree</td> <td>16.7%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Percentage	Strongly agree	83.3%	Agree	16.7%
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<p>How would you rate the visual of the presentations</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ● Satisfaction ● Poor ● Very Poor ●</p>	<table border="1"> <tr><th>Response</th><th>Percentage</th></tr> <tr><td>Excellent</td><td>83.3%</td></tr> <tr><td>Good</td><td>16.7%</td></tr> </table>	Response	Percentage	Excellent	83.3%	Good	16.7%
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Excellent	83.3%						
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Response	Percentage						
Excellent	83.3%						
Good	16.7%						
<p>How would you rate the quality of the visiting lecture</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ● Satisfaction ● Poor ● Very Poor ●</p>	<table border="1"> <tr><th>Response</th><th>Percentage</th></tr> <tr><td>Excellent</td><td>75%</td></tr> <tr><td>Good</td><td>25%</td></tr> </table>	Response	Percentage	Excellent	75%	Good	25%
Response	Percentage						
Excellent	75%						
Good	25%						

2.7.3.2. Visiting Lecture Evaluation by the Lecturer

After the visiting lectures, here are the evaluations by the visiting lecturer Dr. Ó'hannracháin

Questionnaire					
<p>I had enough time to prepare my presentation.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ● Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>	<table border="1"> <tr><th>Response</th><th>Percentage</th></tr> <tr><td>Strongly agree</td><td>100%</td></tr> </table>	Response	Percentage	Strongly agree	100%
Response	Percentage				
Strongly agree	100%				

<p>The time allowed for the visiting lecture was appropriate.</p> <p>Strongly agree	
<p>The content presented was appropriate to the visiting lecture objectives.</p> <p>Strongly agree	
<p>The content presented was compatible with students' needs.</p> <p>Strongly agree	
<p>The students were interested and enthusiastic.</p> <p>Strongly agree	
<p>I was able to encourage critical thinking and problem-solving.</p> <p>Strongly agree	
<p>The teaching environment met all visiting lecture needs.</p> <p>Strongly agree	
<p>I received positive feedback from faculty members and students after the visiting lecture.</p> <p>Strongly agree	

<p>How do you rate the overall organisation of REMODEL visiting lecture (registration, schedule, communication etc.)</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ● Satisfaction ●</p> <p>Poor ● Very Poor ●</p>	
<p>How do you rate the overall students' attitudes towards the visiting lecture</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ● Satisfaction ●</p> <p>Poor ● Very Poor ●</p>	
<p>How do you rate your overall visiting lecture experience</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ● Satisfaction ●</p> <p>Poor ● Very Poor ●</p>	

2.12. Scope of the Twelfth Staff Exchange (Understanding Horizon Europe – ATU)

The last REMODEL Visiting Lecture named “Understanding Horizon Europe – Funding, Priorities & Participation” organized by ATU on May 27th, 2025 at BUU FEAS.

2.12.1. Visiting Lecturer and Contents

Juanita provided the participants with an introduction to Horizon Europe, the European Union’s main research and innovation funding programme.

Juanita Blue

Juanita Blue is Atlantic Technological University’s Senior European Project Officer. She has Extensive experience as a Programme Manager, leader and managing European funded projects under Horizon, Interreg, and Erasmus+. She advises researchers how to successfully access EU funding, and how to manage awarded projects. She also manages various EU funded projects across multiple disciplines on behalf of ATU. She holds a B.Sc. (hons) in Computer Security & Digital Forensics. As part of her ongoing Ph.D., she has conducted extensive research in the areas of Intelligent Identity Authentication and Intelligent Agents. Her work has been disseminated at forums both nationally and internationally. Juanita is an accomplished

lecturer in the areas of Computer Security; Risk, Governance & Compliance; Biometrics; and Maths for Cryptography. Juanita specializes in projects with a digital theme and digital transformation technologies, and has extensive knowledge and experience in the area of sustainability and SDG education/implementation.

In this visiting lecture session, the fundamental elements of the programme, practical insights on stakeholder engagement, strategies for building strong partnerships, and the alignment of project ideas with EU priorities were addressed. Participants explored the programme’s three key pillars, six thematic clusters, and its focus on “Widening Participation” and “Strengthening the European Research Area (ERA).” Through this content, the following learning outcomes were expected:

- Understand the objectives and structure of Horizon Europe.
- Become familiar with the thematic clusters
- Explore Widening Participation & ERA
- Align Projects with EU Priorities

Juanita is talking about "EU Priorities & HE Clusters"

2.12.2. Participants

Visiting lecture is open to participation of all PhD students and early-stage researchers registered in Bursa Uludag University. 54 PhD students and early-stage researchers attended the visiting lecture on "Understanding Horizon Europe – Funding, Priorities & Participation" held on May 27th, 2025. The distribution of early-stage researchers and PhD students participating in the visiting lecture by departments and gender are as follows:

		Participants	Numbers
		<i>Early-stage researchers</i>	53
Departments of PhD students participating in the visiting lecture		Numbers	
		<i>Business Administration</i>	1
		TOTAL	54
Gender of Participants in the Visiting Lecture		Numbers	
		<i>Male</i>	30
		<i>Female</i>	24
		TOTAL	54

Juanita Blue and Participants

2.12.3. Visiting Lecture Evaluation

Visiting lecture evaluation forms were prepared for both participants and the visiting lecturer to evaluate the visiting lecture. At the end of the visiting lecture, the forms were sent online to the participants and the visiting lecturer.

2.12.3.1. Visiting Lecture Evaluation by the Participants

After the visiting lecture on "Understanding Horizon Europe – Funding, Priorities & Participation", 12 participants evaluated. The evaluations of the participants are as follows:

Questionnaire							
<p>The agenda of the visiting lecture was satisfactory.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ● Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>	<table border="1" data-bbox="1018 1400 1257 1630"> <tr><th>Response</th><th>Percentage</th></tr> <tr><td>Strongly agree</td><td>83.3%</td></tr> <tr><td>Agree</td><td>16.7%</td></tr> </table>	Response	Percentage	Strongly agree	83.3%	Agree	16.7%
Response	Percentage						
Strongly agree	83.3%						
Agree	16.7%						
<p>The lecturer was knowledgeable about the visiting lecture topics.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ● Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>	<table border="1" data-bbox="1018 1668 1257 1899"> <tr><th>Response</th><th>Percentage</th></tr> <tr><td>Strongly agree</td><td>75%</td></tr> <tr><td>Agree</td><td>25%</td></tr> </table>	Response	Percentage	Strongly agree	75%	Agree	25%
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<p>The lecturer was well prepared.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ● Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Strongly agree</td> <td>83.3%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Agree</td> <td>16.7%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Percentage	Strongly agree	83.3%	Agree	16.7%		
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Agree	16.7%								
<p>The content was well-organised and easy to follow.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ● Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Strongly agree</td> <td>83.3%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Agree</td> <td>16.7%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Percentage	Strongly agree	83.3%	Agree	16.7%		
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<p>The time allocated for visiting lecture was sufficient.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ● Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Strongly agree</td> <td>83.3%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Agree</td> <td>16.7%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Percentage	Strongly agree	83.3%	Agree	16.7%		
Response	Percentage								
Strongly agree	83.3%								
Agree	16.7%								
<p>The visiting lecture content met my expectations.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ● Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Strongly agree</td> <td>83.3%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Agree</td> <td>16.7%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Percentage	Strongly agree	83.3%	Agree	16.7%		
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<p>Participation and interaction were encouraged.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ● Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Strongly agree</td> <td>75%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Agree</td> <td>16.7%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Neutral</td> <td>8.3%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Percentage	Strongly agree	75%	Agree	16.7%	Neutral	8.3%
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Strongly agree	75%								
Agree	16.7%								
Neutral	8.3%								
<p>This visiting lecture experience will be useful in my work.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ● Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Strongly agree</td> <td>75%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Agree</td> <td>25%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Percentage	Strongly agree	75%	Agree	25%		
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<p>The learning environment met all visiting lecture needs.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ● Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Strongly agree</td> <td>75%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Agree</td> <td>16.7%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Neutral</td> <td>8.3%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Percentage	Strongly agree	75%	Agree	16.7%	Neutral	8.3%
Response	Percentage								
Strongly agree	75%								
Agree	16.7%								
Neutral	8.3%								

<p>I would recommend REMODEL visiting lecture to other people.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ● Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>	<table border="1"> <tr><th>Response</th><th>Percentage</th></tr> <tr><td>Strongly agree</td><td>83.3%</td></tr> <tr><td>Agree</td><td>16.7%</td></tr> </table>	Response	Percentage	Strongly agree	83.3%	Agree	16.7%		
Response	Percentage								
Strongly agree	83.3%								
Agree	16.7%								
<p>How would you rate the overall organisation of REMODEL visiting lecture (registration, schedule, organisation etc.)</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ● Satisfaction ● Poor ● Very Poor ●</p>	<table border="1"> <tr><th>Response</th><th>Percentage</th></tr> <tr><td>Excellent</td><td>83.3%</td></tr> <tr><td>Good</td><td>16.7%</td></tr> </table>	Response	Percentage	Excellent	83.3%	Good	16.7%		
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<p>How would you rate the visual of the presentations</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ● Satisfaction ● Poor ● Very Poor ●</p>	<table border="1"> <tr><th>Response</th><th>Percentage</th></tr> <tr><td>Excellent</td><td>75%</td></tr> <tr><td>Good</td><td>16.7%</td></tr> <tr><td>Satisfaction</td><td>8.3%</td></tr> </table>	Response	Percentage	Excellent	75%	Good	16.7%	Satisfaction	8.3%
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Satisfaction	8.3%								
<p>How do you rate the quality of presentations</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ● Satisfaction ● Poor ● Very Poor ●</p>	<table border="1"> <tr><th>Response</th><th>Percentage</th></tr> <tr><td>Excellent</td><td>83.3%</td></tr> <tr><td>Good</td><td>16.7%</td></tr> </table>	Response	Percentage	Excellent	83.3%	Good	16.7%		
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<p>How would you rate the quality of the visiting lecture</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ● Satisfaction ● Poor ● Very Poor ●</p>	<table border="1"> <tr><th>Response</th><th>Percentage</th></tr> <tr><td>Excellent</td><td>75%</td></tr> <tr><td>Good</td><td>25%</td></tr> </table>	Response	Percentage	Excellent	75%	Good	25%		
Response	Percentage								
Excellent	75%								
Good	25%								

2.12.3.2. Visiting Lecture Evaluation by the Lecturer

After the visiting lectures, here are the evaluations by the visiting lecturer Dr. Blue:

Questionnaire					
<p>I had enough time to prepare my presentation.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ● Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>	<table border="1"> <tr><th>Response</th><th>Percentage</th></tr> <tr><td>Strongly agree</td><td>100%</td></tr> </table>	Response	Percentage	Strongly agree	100%
Response	Percentage				
Strongly agree	100%				

<p>The time allowed for the visiting lecture was appropriate.</p> <p>Strongly agree	
<p>The content presented was appropriate to the visiting lecture objectives.</p> <p>Strongly agree	
<p>The content presented was compatible with students' needs.</p> <p>Strongly agree	
<p>The students were interested and enthusiastic.</p> <p>Strongly agree	
<p>I was able to encourage critical thinking and problem-solving.</p> <p>Strongly agree	
<p>The teaching environment met all visiting lecture needs.</p> <p>Strongly agree	
<p>I received positive feedback from faculty members and students after the visiting lecture.</p> <p>Strongly agree	

<p>How do you rate the overall organisation of REMODEL visiting lecture (registration, schedule, communication etc.)</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ● Satisfaction ●</p> <p>Poor ● Very Poor ●</p>	<p>100%</p>
<p>How do you rate the overall students' attitudes towards the visiting lecture</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ● Satisfaction ●</p> <p>Poor ● Very Poor ●</p>	<p>100%</p>
<p>How do you rate your overall visiting lecture experience</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ● Satisfaction ●</p> <p>Poor ● Very Poor ●</p>	<p>100%</p>

3. Summer School Report

3.1. Scope of the First Summer School (Sustainability & Tourism Challenges – ULE)

The first REMODEL Summer School (online) named “Sustainability & Tourism Challenges” organized by ULE on July 12th - 13th, 2023. This summer school was conducted online and featured speakers of recognized international prestige and high competence. The general topics discussed are as follows:

- Understanding and predicting consumer tourism responses: The synergy of implicit measures and artificial intelligence
- The science of experiences from a consumer neuro-marketing approach
- Adapting models and frameworks to incorporate TBL-based sustainability
- Mind the Gap: How to communicate with the travellers of today

The topics for the First Summer School, specifically "Sustainability & Tourism Challenges," were chosen by the Consortium based on their critical relevance to both academic inquiry and industry practices in Turkey. This focus aligns with global sustainability goals and addresses pressing challenges in the tourism sector, a significant component of Turkey's economy. Academically, this topic invites exploration of innovative solutions and sustainable practices, fostering interdisciplinary research that merges tourism studies, environmental science, and business. For instance, understanding consumer tourism responses through implicit measures and AI, as discussed by Thomas Zoega Ramsøy, demonstrates how cutting-edge methodologies can predict consumer behavior, informing sustainable tourism strategies. Additionally, Edel Moore's insights into consumer neuromarketing highlight the importance of understanding emotional and cognitive drivers, which can enhance marketing strategies and consumer satisfaction in the tourism sector. For the industry, integrating these innovative practices is crucial for enhancing competitiveness and ensuring sustainable growth. This topic underscores the significance of innovation in developing sustainable tourism strategies, thereby driving effective and sustainable tourism marketing and operations.

3.1.1. Summer School Lecturers and Contents

On the first day of the summer school, Thomas Zoega Ramsøy and Edel Moore shared their extensive knowledge and experiences in their respective fields of expertise during their training. The first day of the summer school received significant attention. Neil Richardson and Dolores Semeraro shared their comprehensive knowledge and expertise in their respective fields during their training on the second day of the summer school, garnering considerable interest on the first day of the program.

3.1.1.1. Thomas Zoëga Ramsøy

Thomas Zoega Ramsøy is the CEO and Founder of Neurons Inc. A neuropsychologist by training and a Ph.D. in neurobiology and neuroimaging, Ramsøy is considered a leading figure in applied neuroscience. In his speech, Ramsøy has aimed to discover an impressive approach to measuring and predicting consumer responses in the tourism industry. His speech offers an in-depth understanding of how implicit measures and AI can be utilized to measure and predict consumer responses in the tourism industry. Attendees will learn how to use implicit measures to capture consumers' implicit attitudes, emotions, and preferences related to travel experiences. Additionally, they will gain insights into how AI algorithms and predictive modelling can be employed to analyse implicit data at scale, uncover hidden insights, and predict

future consumer behaviour. This will help businesses optimize marketing strategies and enhance customer experiences.

The content of the Thomas Zoëga Ramsøy' training:

- The powerful synergy between implicit measures and AI techniques by combining them.
- Valuable insights into subconscious consumer behaviour and the use of artificial intelligence techniques for informed decision-making
- Explanations about how AI enhances the predictive capabilities of implicit measures,
- Accurate models to extract meaningful patterns for predicting consumer behaviour in the tourism domain by developing accurate models

Through this content, the following learning outcomes are expected:

- Explore the theoretical foundations and practical applications of implicit measures in the context of consumer tourism responses.
- Understand the role of AI in enhancing the predictive capabilities of implicit measures and extracting meaningful patterns from implicit data.
- Gain insights into cutting-edge research at the intersection of implicit measures, AI, and tourism, and its implications for future studies.
- Discover how implicit measures can provide valuable insights into consumers' subconscious attitudes and preferences in the tourism industry.
- Learn how to leverage AI techniques to analyse and predict consumer behaviour using implicit data.
- Understand the practical applications of implicit measures and AI in optimizing marketing strategies, personalizing experiences, and improving business outcomes in the tourism sector.

Relevance for Academics and Industry and Relationship with Innovation:

From an academic standpoint, this talk invites researchers to delve into the realm of implicit measures and AI-driven methodologies in the context of consumer tourism responses. We examine the theoretical foundations and practical applications of implicit measures, which tap into consumers' subconscious attitudes and preferences. Furthermore, we explore how AI can enhance the predictive capabilities of implicit measures, enabling researchers to extract meaningful patterns and develop accurate models for forecasting consumer behavior in the tourism domain.

For industry professionals, this talk presents an opportunity to gain a deep understanding of how implicit measures and AI can be leveraged to measure and predict consumer responses in the tourism industry. Attendees will learn how to utilize implicit measures to capture consumers' implicit attitudes, emotions, and preferences related to travel experiences. Moreover, we delve into how AI algorithms and predictive modeling can be employed to analyze implicit data at scale, uncover hidden insights, and predict future consumer behavior, enabling businesses to optimize marketing strategies and enhance customer experiences.

Key takeaways for the academic audience:

- Explore the theoretical foundations and practical applications of implicit measures in the context of consumer tourism responses.
- Understand the role of AI in enhancing the predictive capabilities of implicit measures and extracting meaningful patterns from implicit data.
- Gain insights into cutting-edge research at the intersection of implicit measures, AI, and tourism, and its implications for future studies.
- Key takeaways for the industry audience:
- Discover how implicit measures can provide valuable insights into consumers' subconscious attitudes and preferences in the tourism industry.
- Learn how to leverage AI techniques to analyze and predict consumer behavior using implicit data.
- Understand the practical applications of implicit measures and AI in optimizing marketing strategies, personalizing experiences, and improving business outcomes in the tourism sector.

By the end of this talk, both academic and industry attendees will gain a comprehensive understanding of how implicit measures and AI can synergistically measure and predict consumer responses in the tourism industry. They will be equipped with valuable knowledge and strategies to integrate implicit measures and AI-driven methodologies into their research and business practices, fostering a deeper understanding of consumer behavior and driving sustainable growth in the tourism sector.

3.1.1.2. Edel Moore

Edel Moore has been worked as a Marketing lecturer in The School of Design, University of Leeds. She conducts research focusing on decision-making in purchasing and retail user experience related to behavioural design, habits, addictions, and real-life situations. Her presentation discusses the possibilities and challenges of utilizing consumer neuromarketing to aid consumer research. Neurotourism is an extremely new and exciting application of cognitive neuroscience techniques and theories to understand consumer decision making, behaviour, and experience perception.

The content of the Edel Moore' training:

- The presentation on Consumer Neuromarketing
- The main neuromarketing tools and benefits of integrating them with traditional consumer research methods
- The pedagogical development of the field outside of the "Psychology Department"
- Potential future research and collaborations between academics, students, and businesses

Through this content, the following learning outcomes are expected:

- Understanding the impact of the phenomenon of Neuromarketing on customers' emotions, thoughts, satisfaction, and actions.
- Learning about the fundamental Neuromarketing tools used to measure psychophysiological responses and integrating them with traditional consumer research methods.
- Understanding the potential for future research and collaborations between academics, students, and businesses.
- Recognizing partnerships aimed at supporting marketing strategies, business development, and sustainability goals in the hospitality and tourism sector.

Relevance for Academics and Industry and Relationship with Innovation:

The course on Consumer Neuromarketing – The Science of Experiences promotes interdisciplinary collaboration, bridging gaps between psychology, neuroscience, marketing, and tourism studies. This fosters a holistic understanding and stimulates innovation in academic research. Businesses in the tourism sector benefit from a deeper understanding of consumer behavior and decision-making processes. Neuromarketing provides insights into the emotional and cognitive factors driving consumer choices, enabling more effective and targeted marketing strategies. Introducing neuromarketing tools and techniques enriches traditional consumer research methods. Academics gain access to cutting-edge methodologies for measuring psychophysiological responses, enhancing the depth and accuracy of their research. By understanding the psychophysiological responses of consumers, businesses can design experiences that resonate emotionally with their customers. This leads to higher satisfaction, loyalty, and positive word-of-mouth, crucial for success in the competitive tourism market. By showcasing the development of neuromarketing education outside traditional psychology departments, the course promotes a multidisciplinary approach to teaching. This broadens the academic curriculum, offering students from diverse faculties new perspectives and skills relevant to the tourism sector. The application of neuromarketing in developing marketing strategies helps businesses optimize their branding, advertising, and service offerings. This strategic use of consumer insights can drive business growth and development, ensuring they stay ahead of market trends. By understanding consumer

preferences and behaviors related to sustainability, businesses can tailor their practices to meet these expectations, fostering a more sustainable and responsible tourism industry.

3.1.1.3. Neil Richardson

Dr. Neil Richardson is an experienced marketing/business practitioner with over 20 years of private sector experience (in B2B Sales Management, Marketing and Customer Service), covering operational and strategic positions. He has worked for (and with) world-class companies in differing sectors. He has been a director of a social enterprise as well as other SMEs. The main topic of his speech is to adapt well-established models or frameworks to incorporate the TBL and he focuses on customer loyalty and the consumer decision-making process.

The content of the Neil Richardson' training:

- The traditional model and framework
 - Creating a model and framework where the TBL is fully integrated
- TBL Based Sustainability and importance of sustainability in business
 - Overview of traditional models and framework and benefits of incorporating TBL into them

Through this content, the following learning outcomes are expected:

- The fundamental outcomes of the training can be summarized as follows.
- To determine the potential of integrating TBL with existing models and frameworks.
- To explain sustainable practices, responsible decision-making processes, and the process of creating long-term value.
- To demonstrate how organizations can enhance their overall sustainability efforts by integrating TBL principles into their existing strategies and frameworks.

Relevance for Academics and Industry and Relationship with Innovation:

This course enriches academic discourse by integrating the Triple Bottom Line (TBL) into established models and frameworks. This adaptation fosters a more comprehensive understanding of sustainability within the consumer decision-making process (DMP) and loyalty frameworks, which is essential for contemporary academic research. Academics can leverage the adapted TBL models to pursue innovative research projects. These projects can explore new dimensions of consumer behavior, loyalty, and sustainability, contributing valuable insights to the academic community and beyond. The course content supports the development of a progressive curriculum that incorporates sustainability into business education. This aligns with the increasing demand for sustainability education and prepares students for the evolving job market where sustainable practices are valued.

For business professionals, understanding how to adapt traditional models to incorporate TBL principles is crucial for developing sustainable business strategies. This knowledge helps companies align their operations with global sustainability goals, enhancing their competitive edge and long-term viability. By integrating sustainability into the consumer decision-making process, businesses can build stronger, more loyal customer bases. Consumers are increasingly prioritizing sustainability, and companies that reflect these values in their business models are likely to see increased loyalty and positive brand perception. Businesses that incorporate TBL into their models can innovate and differentiate themselves in the market as leaders in sustainability. This not only attracts a growing segment of environmentally and socially conscious consumers but also fosters innovation in product development, marketing, and corporate social responsibility (CSR) initiatives.

3.1.1.4. Dolores Semeraro

Dolores Semeraro is a sought-after international tourism keynote speaker and tourism marketing professional. Italian by origin, she is fluent in Chinese and English with a bachelor's degree in translation and interpreting. In the scope of her speech, considering the recent global events that have deeply shaken the tourism and travel industry, the determination of how the future of travel training program should be structured has been made.

The content of the Dolores Semeraro' training:

- The changes that industry operators need to make to create resilient marketing strategies, and the importance of developing a traveller-centric mind-set
- The impacts of global uncertainties on travellers' brand trust, market positioning, and the desired financial outcomes of tourism and hospitality operators
- The benefits of communicating on the value-point instead of the price-point of sustainability choices for travel and tourism
- Metaverse traveller experiences and techniques for accessing the Metaverse.

Through this content, the following learning outcomes are expected:

- Going beyond the typical "who is your ideal customer" question in the tourism sector and developing a trustworthy and inspiring approach in post-pandemic travellers.
- Learning the necessary changes in the travel and tourism industry and the evolving corporate communication strategies following the emergence of the COVID-19 pandemic.
- Identifying the distinct characteristics, concerns, and expectations observed in post-pandemic travellers.
- Analysing the intricacies of communicating with evolved travellers.

Relevance for Academics and Industry and Relationship with Innovation:

By addressing the impact of recent global events on the travel industry, the course ensures that academic curricula remain current and responsive to real-world challenges. This training program highlights new areas for academic research, such as the effects of global uncertainty on traveler behavior and brand trust. Researchers can explore these topics further, contributing to the body of knowledge in tourism studies and providing insights that can inform industry practices. The course's focus on marketing, consumer behavior, and strategic adaptation intersects with disciplines such as psychology, business, and communication studies. This promotes interdisciplinary learning and helps students understand the multifaceted nature of tourism and hospitality management.

Business professionals in the tourism sector can benefit from learning how to create marketing strategies that are resilient to global uncertainties. This ensures that businesses can maintain and build brand trust, even in times of crisis, which is crucial for long-term success. Adopting a traveler-centric approach helps businesses align their offerings with the evolving needs and expectations of post-pandemic travelers. This shift can enhance customer satisfaction, loyalty, and ultimately drive financial performance. The seminar provides insights into developing a tone of voice that inspires trust among travelers. This is vital for rebuilding and maintaining brand trust, which has been significantly affected by recent global events. Businesses can learn to position themselves effectively in the market by addressing the concerns and priorities of modern travelers.

3.1.2. Participants

The REMODEL online summer school organized by ULE received significant interest from academics, researchers, and practitioners. There was a great interest in the summer school, and 70 participants registered. Some Information about the participants from different countries and different professional groups is as follows:

<i>Country</i>	<i>Number of Participants</i>
<i>Austria</i>	3
<i>Canada</i>	1
<i>Equator</i>	1
<i>Greece</i>	1
<i>India</i>	2
<i>Ireland</i>	6
<i>Italy</i>	1
<i>Montenegro</i>	1
<i>Nepal</i>	1
<i>Norway</i>	1
<i>Portugal</i>	1
<i>Spain</i>	30
<i>Turkey</i>	16
<i>Thailand</i>	1
<i>UK</i>	2
<i>USA</i>	2
Total	70
<i>Professional Categories</i>	<i>Number of Participants</i>
<i>Company Manager / Employer</i>	20
<i>Professor /Researcher</i>	31
<i>Student</i>	19
Total	70

A total of 43 participants actively participated for the first day. But unfortunately, Edel couldn't deliver her speech during the training hour because of some health problem and she shared her speech with the participants as a video. Information about the attendees are as follows:

<i>Date</i>	<i>Speaker</i>	<i>Topic</i>	<i>No attendees</i>	<i>Male</i>	<i>Female</i>
July 2023 12th,	ThomasZoega Ramsøy	Understanding and predicting consumer tourism responses: The synergy of implicit measures and AI	43	17	26
	Edel Moore	The science of experiences from a consumer neuromarketing approach			
July 2023 13th,	Neil Richardson	Adapting models and frameworks to incorporate TBL-based sustainability	37	14	23
	Dolores Semeraro	Mind the Gap: How to communicate with the travelers of today			

<i>Country</i>	<i>Number of attendees</i>
<i>Austria</i>	2
<i>India</i>	1
<i>Ireland</i>	5
<i>Montenegro</i>	1
<i>Spain</i>	27
<i>Turkey</i>	7
Total	43

<i>Professional Categories</i>	<i>Number of attendees</i>
<i>Company Manager / Employer</i>	16
<i>Professor /Researcher</i>	18
<i>Student</i>	9
Total	43

<i>Country</i>	<i>Number of attendees</i>
<i>Ireland</i>	4
<i>Montenegro</i>	1
<i>Spain</i>	20
<i>Turkey</i>	12
Total	37

<i>Professional Categories</i>	<i>Number of attendees</i>
<i>Company Manager / Employer</i>	8
<i>Professor /Researcher</i>	24
<i>Student</i>	5
Total	37

“Thomas Zoëga Ramsøy talked about The Synergy of Implicit Measures and Artificial Intelligence”

“Edel Moore provided detailed information about Consumer Neuromarketing.”

On the second day of the summer school first Neil Richardson conducted a presentation titled "Adapting Models and Frameworks to Incorporate TBL." In the afternoon, Dolores Semeraro shared information and experiences on how to communicate with travellers. A total of 37 participants actively participated for the second day of the summer school.

“Neil discussed Triple Bottom Line with the participants.”

“Dolores Semeraro gave information on how to communicate with today’s travellers.”

3.1.3. Summer School Evaluation

Summer school evaluation forms were prepared for both participants and speakers to assess the training provided during the summer school. At the end of the session, the forms were sent online to both participants and speakers.

3.1.3.1. Summer School Evaluation by the Participants

After the training sessions, evaluations were conducted by 26 participants for Thomas Zoega Ramsoy, 17 participants for Neil Richardson, and 19 participants for Dolores Semeraro. The participants' assessments are as follows:

Questionnaire	T.Z. RAMSOY	N. Richardson	D. Semeraro
<p>The agenda of the training was satisfactory.</p> <p>Strongly agree Agree </p> <p>Neutral Disagree </p> <p>Strongly disagree </p>			
<p>The lecturer was knowledgeable about the training topics.</p> <p>Strongly agree Agree </p> <p>Neutral Disagree </p> <p>Strongly disagree </p>			
<p>The lecturer was well prepared.</p> <p>Strongly agree Agree </p> <p>Neutral Disagree </p> <p>Strongly disagree </p>			
<p>The content was well-organised and easy to follow</p> <p>Strongly agree Agree </p> <p>Neutral Disagree </p> <p>Strongly disagree </p>			
<p>The lecturer provided interesting examples from his/her experience</p> <p>Strongly agree Agree </p> <p>Neutral Disagree </p> <p>Strongly disagree </p>			

<p>I consider the expertise of the lecturer</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ●</p> <p>Neutral ● Disagree ●</p> <p>Strongly disagree ●</p>			
<p>The time allocated for training was sufficient.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ●</p> <p>Neutral ● Disagree ●</p> <p>Strongly disagree ●</p>			
<p>The training content met my expectations</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ●</p> <p>Neutral ● Disagree ●</p> <p>Strongly disagree ●</p>			
<p>Participation and interaction were encouraged.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ●</p> <p>Neutral ● Disagree ●</p> <p>Strongly disagree ●</p>			
<p>This training experience will be useful in my work.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ●</p> <p>Neutral ● Disagree ●</p> <p>Strongly disagree ●</p>			
<p>The online learning environment met all training needs</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ●</p> <p>Neutral ● Disagree ●</p> <p>Strongly disagree ●</p>			

<p>I would recommend REMODEL summer school to other people.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ●</p> <p>Neutral ● Disagree ●</p> <p>Strongly disagree ●</p>			
<p>How would you rate the overall organisation of REMODEL summer school (registration, schedule, organisation etc.)</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ●</p> <p>Satisfaction ● Poor ●</p> <p>Very poor ●</p>			
<p>How would you rate the visual of the presentations</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ●</p> <p>Satisfaction ● Poor ●</p> <p>Very poor ●</p>			
<p>How do you rate the quality of presentations</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ●</p> <p>Satisfaction ● Poor ●</p> <p>Very poor ●</p>			
<p>How would you rate the quality of the lecturer</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ●</p> <p>Satisfaction ● Poor ●</p> <p>Very poor ●</p>			

3.1.3.2. Summer School Evaluation by the Lecturers

Also, after the trainings the lecturer evaluation surveys were sent to Thomas Zoega Ramsøy, Neil Richardson and Dolores Semeraro and the survey results day by day are as follows:

Questionnaire	First Day	Second Day
<p>I had enough time to prepare my presentation.</p> <p>Strongly agree		
<p>The time allowed for the training was appropriate.</p> <p>Strongly agree		
<p>The content presented was appropriate to the training objectives.</p> <p>Strongly agree		
<p>The content presented was compatible with students' needs.</p> <p>Strongly agree		
<p>The students were interested and enthusiastic.</p> <p>Strongly agree		
<p>I was able to encourage critical thinking and problem-solving.</p> <p>Strongly agree		

<p>The online training environment met all training needs.</p> <p>Strongly agree		
<p>I received positive feedback from faculty members and students after the training.</p> <p>Strongly agree		
<p>How do you rate the overall organisation of REMODEL summer school (registration, schedule, communication etc.)</p> <p>Excellent		
<p>How do you rate the overall students' attitudes towards the training</p> <p>Excellent		
<p>How do you rate your overall training experience</p> <p>Excellent		

3.2. Scope of the Second Summer School (Sustainable Rural Tourism – ATU)

The second summer school on “Sustainable Rural Tourism” is scheduled for June 6-7, 2024. It is organized by the Atlantic Technological University (ATU) in collaboration with the REMODEL project. The primary aim of the summer school was to explore sustainable tourism practices, focusing on rural areas. This event aims to help participants understand the best practices in sustainable tourism and develop their own regional applications.

The scope of the summer school is quite broad, covering a variety of topics. These topics include:

- Sustainable tourism certification,
- Sustainable destination management,
- Gastronomy tourism,
- Community engagement,
- Tourism policies and planning strategies.

The summer school continued for two days, with training sessions conducted on the first day featuring expert speakers in their fields. On the second day, visits were made to the Radisson Blu Hotel and Glenveagh National Park for field research. During these visits, sustainable tourism and management practices were explored on-site. During the visit, Radisson Blu Hotel's Managing Director Paul Byrne and Head of Education & Learning Glenveagh National Park Clara Bromley shared valuable practical insights with the participants.

3.2.1. Summer School Lecturers and Contents

On The first day of our summer school offered a rich program featuring various speakers focusing on sustainable tourism and the publishing process. Prof. Thomas Fletcher (Leeds Beckett University, United Kingdom) delivered a presentation titled "Meet the Editor - Demystifying the Publication Process," which aimed to simplify the understanding of the publication process and highlight key considerations in academic writing. Dr. Mihee Kang (GSTC Global Assurance and Asia Pacific Director) gave a talk on "The Opportunities and Benefits of GSTC Certification," discussing sustainable tourism certification and case studies from Türkiye. Charlene Boyle (Fáilte Ireland) presented "The Wild Atlantic Way," outlining the goals of the Wild Atlantic Way project and strategies for community engagement. Dr. James Hanrahan (ATU Sligo and Director of ASTOI) discussed sustainable tourism policies and management approaches in his presentation, "Introducing STORY ATU's Sustainable Tourism and Visitor Economy Laboratory." Lastly, Jacinta Dalton (ATU Galway) presented on "Food and Beverage as a Niche Tourism Product," focusing on the development of food tourism and significant case studies in the field. These presentations provided participants with diverse perspectives and practical insights on the first day of the summer school.

3.2.1.1. Thomas Fletcher

Thomas Fletcher is professor in the School of Events, Tourism and Hospitality Management and Carnegie School of Sport at Leeds Beckett University, United Kingdom. He is an interdisciplinary applied sociologist with particular interest in sport, equity, diversity and inclusion, social justice, families and fatherhood. Tom is the author of the award-winning book *Negotiating Fatherhood: Sport and Family Practices* (Palgrave Macmillan). He has a range of roles with international peer review journals and organisations. He is currently a Managing Editor of *Leisure Studies*, Associate Editor of *Events Management and Sport in Society*. He was previously Reviews Editor for *Soccer & Society*. Tom is a Board member of The Academy of Leisure Sciences and sits on the Heritage Advisory Group of the Yorkshire Cricket Foundation. Between 2017 and 2020 Tom was Chair of the

Leisure Studies Association. His session named "Meet the Editor - Demystifying the Publication Process" focuses on understanding the perspectives of journal editors and reviewers for researchers who wish to grasp the publication process. It explains the concepts of "contributing" and "adding to the body of knowledge" in publications, analyzes the peer-review process, and examines the reasons for rejections.

Through this content, the following learning outcomes are expected:

Understanding the perspective of journals and editors.

- Grasping the concept of contributing and adding to the body of knowledge in publications.
- Learning how to respond to reviewer comments.
- Understanding the reasons for rejection and what should be avoided.

Relevance for Academics and Industry and Relationship with Innovation:

This training holds significant importance in promoting innovation in both academia and industry. For academics and researchers, understanding the publication process and the perspectives of editors and reviewers is a critical competency in making more effective scientific contributions and introducing innovative research to the literature. In this session, strategies were presented that enable academics and professionals, particularly those working in sustainable rural tourism and the hospitality sector, to effectively disseminate their innovative ideas.

From an industry perspective, academic research plays a crucial role in the development and implementation of new business models. This training has contributed to promoting sustainability and innovation by helping industry professionals better understand and integrate innovative discoveries from academia into their business processes. Additionally, understanding the challenges within the research process for both academics and industry professionals paves the way for collaborations and innovative solutions. This session provided significant contributions to the development of participants in both academia and the hospitality sector in terms of strengthening innovation and achieving sustainability goals.

3.2.1.2. Mihee Kang

Dr. Mihee Kang is the GSTC Director of Global Assurance as well as Director for the Asia Pacific region and is active as an authorized GSTC trainer and destination assessor. A trailblazer, Dr Kang was the first person to earn a PhD in ecotourism in Korea from Seoul National University and she retains links with several universities where she actively teaches, conducts research and publishes on the topics of ecotourism and sustainable tourism. Mihee has been involved in sustainable tourism policy development and sustainability assessments of various types of destinations in S. Korea and other countries over 30 years. She has served in both domestic and international organizations such as Korean Geopark Committee, Korea Islands Foundation, Korea Trails and Culture, Jeju World Heritage Committee, Korea Forest Education Committee and the Global Ecotourism Network.

The session named ""The Opportunities and Benefits of GSTC Certification" provides information on sustainable tourism certification and the GSTC certification program. It addresses the importance of third-party audit control and explores the opportunities and benefits that certification offers to tourism businesses, destinations, and governments.

Through this content, the following learning outcomes are expected:

- Understanding sustainable tourism certification and the GSTC program.
- Grasping the importance of third-party audit control.
- Evaluating the opportunities and benefits that certification offers to the tourism sector.
- Gaining practical insights through a GSTC case study in Turkey.

Relevance for Academics and Industry and Relationship with Innovation:

This training offered an important opportunity for participants to enhance their development in both academic and industrial contexts regarding the certification of sustainable tourism. For academia, understanding the importance of Global Sustainable Tourism Council (GSTC) certification and third-party auditing plays a critical role in advancing sustainability research and developing innovative work in this field. Certification programs contribute to the development of innovative strategies for the implementation and dissemination of sustainability standards. By examining these certification processes, academics can create more effective sustainability solutions and innovative practices for the tourism sector. For the tourism industry, GSTC certification is seen as an innovation that provides a competitive advantage in the business world. Certification programs help businesses, destinations, and governments secure their sustainability commitments while offering innovative opportunities to the sector. These certifications not only promote environmental sustainability but also contribute to economic and social sustainability, thereby fostering innovation within the tourism industry. This session provided a crucial platform for strengthening sustainability and innovation at both academic and sectoral levels.

3.2.1.2. Charlene Boyle

Charlene Boyle from Fáilte Ireland is an insight driven, strategic marketer with extensive experience leading and implementing communication and marketing campaigns within the public and private sector. She has an in-depth knowledge of international markets having worked across Tourism Ireland's overseas network for more than 10 years. However, the call of home was strong, and in 2020, Charlene returned to Donegal with her family, taking up a role within Fáilte Ireland's Wild Atlantic Way team. Promoting the regions natural beauty and fostering sustainable tourism development.

Her session named "The Wild Atlantic Way" focuses on the aim and context of the Wild Atlantic Way project in 2014.

It also discusses the products used in the project, community involvement, discovery points, branding, and the successes achieved.

Through this content, the following learning outcomes are expected:

- Understanding the purpose and content of the Wild Atlantic Way project.
- Evaluating the role of community involvement and discovery points in the project.
- Understanding Fáilte Ireland's priorities and future opportunities.

Relevance for Academics and Industry and Relationship with Innovation:

This training presents valuable lessons in tourism projects and innovative approaches in both academic and industrial contexts. For academics, this project serves as a case study showing how sustainable tourism strategies can succeed by developing a deep understanding of community engagement, discovery points, and branding processes. Moreover, Fáilte Ireland's priorities and future opportunities in the project offer new perspectives for academic research.

From an industry standpoint, the "Wild Atlantic Way" project is a vivid example of how community engagement can create innovative value, particularly in the tourism sector. The products and discovery points used in the project inspire the development of new business models for the industry by promoting differentiation in tourism and collaboration with local communities. In this context, the project serves as a significant reference for sector professionals in terms of innovative branding and transforming local values into international success. This session provided inspiring examples of how innovative business models can be implemented in the tourism industry and new research opportunities for academic work.

3.2.1.2. James Hanrahan

James Hanrahan BA, MSc, PhD is currently a lecturer in Tourism Management in the School of Business and Social Science at Atlantic Technological University Sligo. He has worked as a tour guide, tour operator, tourism manager, tourism entrepreneur, tourism consultant and lecturer in Ireland, New Zealand, Hawaii, Bulgaria, California, and Britain. He has a key set of publications related to sustainable destination management and an established track record in research supervision at PhD level.

James applies this research through his work for the public and private sector in tourism planning and development. He is Director of the recently created Atlantic Sustainable Tourism Observatory Ireland using UN Tourism, GSTC and European Tourism Indicator

System (ETIS) for Sustainable Destination management, this STO is one of only 44 in the world. James actively collaborates with Failte Ireland, Clare, Donegal and Galway County Councils, EarthCheck, and the network of internationally recognized UN Tourism sustainable tourism observatories.

The session named "Introducing STORY ATU's Sustainable Tourism and Visitor Economy Laboratory" focuses on tourism policies in Europe and Ireland and sustainable tourism measurement mechanisms. It also provides insights into STORY's role as a partner for sustainable destinations and highlights key indicators.

Through this content, the following learning outcomes are expected:

- Understanding the tourism policies and regulations of Europe and Ireland.
- Grasping global measurement mechanisms for sustainable tourism.
- Evaluating the role of STORY as a sustainable tourism laboratory.

Relevance for Academics and Industry and Relationship with Innovation:

This training is of great importance in terms of the development of sustainable tourism and innovation in both academic and industrial spheres. In academia, understanding European and Irish tourism policies and global sustainable tourism measurement mechanisms enables the development of new research opportunities and innovative approaches in sustainable destination management. From an industry perspective, measuring and managing sustainable tourism is crucial for the development of innovative business models. Laboratories like the one led by James, such as STORY, offer new tools for the effective implementation of sustainable destination management and tourism policies. This session provided a comprehensive guide for public and private sector professionals on implementing sustainability standards, promoting innovation, and sustainable business models in the tourism sector. The session presented critical insights encouraging both academic research on sustainable tourism policies and the development of innovative and sustainable solutions in the tourism industry.

3.2.1.2. Jacinta Dalton

Jacinta Dalton is Head of Department for Culinary Arts & Service Industries at The Atlantic Technological University, Galway, Ireland and is a member of the Irish Food Champion Assembly. She is an advocate for food education, innovation and community engagement for knowledge exchange and sustainability, consulting with food producers, and assisting with a number of food events and festivals in a voluntary capacity. Jacinta is currently undertaking a Doctorate at the Basque Culinary Centre, where she is researching the impacts of public food procurement on sustainable education and is working on an Erasmus project with European partners on the development of digital and sustainability skills for Tourism SME's. Jacinta is a board member at the Institute of Gastronomy, Culture, Arts & Tourism (IGCAT).

Her session named "Food and Beverage as a Niche Tourism Product" focuses on the development of food tourism and its impact on people, culture, heritage, and traditions. Case studies from the Basque Country and Ireland are presented.

Through this content, the following learning outcomes are expected:

- Understanding the development and impacts of food tourism.
- Evaluating key trends and case studies in food tourism.
- Understanding the role and future opportunities of F&B tourism in Ireland.

Relevance for Academics and Industry and Relationship with Innovation

This training, offering great innovative opportunities for both academia and the tourism industry, provides academics with an important opportunity to deeply examine the development of food tourism and its impacts on communities, culture, heritage, and traditions. Case studies from the Basque Country and Ireland have contributed new perspectives to the academic literature by analyzing the socio-cultural impacts of food tourism. Food tourism is recognized in academic research as an innovative field that needs to be studied in terms of both cultural sustainability and the strengthening of local economies. For the industry, food and beverage tourism opens the door to innovation as a niche product that allows for the differentiation of destinations. The case studies presented in this session, particularly through the example of Ireland, demonstrate the future opportunities of food tourism in the tourism sector and its contributions to local economies. Food tourism provides tourism businesses with an important opportunity to promote cultural heritage and develop sustainable business models with local food and beverage products. This session has shown how food tourism can be a significant tool for innovative business models and sustainable development at both academic and sectoral levels.

3.2.2. Participants

The REMODEL online summer school organized by ATU received significant interest from academics, researchers, and practitioners. There was a great interest in the summer school, and 55 participants registered. 22 participants continued the training online. Some Information about the participants from project partner countries and different professional groups is as follows:

<i>Country</i>	<i>Number of Participants</i>
<i>Ireland</i>	39
<i>Spain</i>	4
<i>Turkey</i>	12
Total	55
<i>Professional Categories</i>	<i>Number of Participants</i>
<i>Company Manager / Employer/ Tourism Practitioner Professor /Researcher</i>	10
<i>Student</i>	5
Total	55
<i>Professional Categories</i>	<i>Number of Participants</i>
<i>Female</i>	36
<i>Male</i>	19
Total	55

"The participants argued the training topics"

3.2.3. Summer School Evaluation

Summer school evaluation forms were prepared for both participants and speakers to assess the training provided during the summer school. At the end of the session, the forms were sent online to both participants and speakers.

3.2.3.1. Summer School Evaluation by the Participants

After the training sessions, evaluations were conducted by 24 participants for Thomas Fletcher and 20 participants for Mihee Kang, Charlene Boyle, James Hanrahan and Jacinta Dalton. The participants' assessments are as follows:

Questionnaire	Thomas Fletcher	Mihee Kang	Charlene Boyle	James Hanrahan	Jacinta Dalton
The agenda of the training was satisfactory.					
Strongly agree	66,7%	80%	80%	60%	80%
Agree	33,3%	20%	20%	40%	20%
Neutral					
Disagree					
Strongly disagree					

<p>The lecturer was knowledgeable about the training topics.</p> <p>Strongly agree					
<p>The lecturer was well prepared.</p> <p>Strongly agree					
<p>The content was well-organised and easy to follow</p> <p>Strongly agree					
<p>The lecturer provided interesting examples from his/her experience</p> <p>Strongly agree					
<p>I consider the expertise of the lecturer</p> <p>Strongly agree					

<p>The time allocated for training was sufficient</p> <p>Strongly agree</p> <p>Agree</p> <p>Neutral</p> <p>Disagree</p> <p>Strongly disagree</p>					
<p>The training content met my expectations</p> <p>Strongly agree</p> <p>Agree</p> <p>Neutral</p> <p>Disagree</p> <p>Strongly disagree</p>					
<p>Participation and interaction were encouraged</p> <p>Strongly agree</p> <p>Agree</p> <p>Neutral</p> <p>Disagree</p> <p>Strongly disagree</p>					
<p>This training experience will be useful in my work</p> <p>Strongly agree</p> <p>Agree</p> <p>Neutral</p> <p>Disagree</p> <p>Strongly disagree</p>					
<p>The physical or online learning environment met all training needs</p> <p>Strongly agree</p> <p>Agree</p> <p>Neutral</p> <p>Disagree</p> <p>Strongly disagree</p>					

<p>I would recommend REMODEL summer school to other people</p> <p>Strongly agree</p> <p>Agree</p> <p>Neutral</p> <p>Disagree</p> <p>Strongly disagree</p>					
<p>How would you rate the overall organisation of REMODEL summer school (registration, schedule, organisation etc.)</p> <p>Excellent</p> <p>Good</p> <p>Satisfaction</p> <p>Poor</p> <p>Very Poor</p>					
<p>How would you rate the visual of the presentations</p> <p>Excellent</p> <p>Good</p> <p>Satisfaction</p> <p>Poor</p> <p>Very Poor</p>					
<p>How do you rate the quality of presentations</p> <p>Excellent</p> <p>Good</p> <p>Satisfaction</p> <p>Poor</p> <p>Very Poor</p>					
<p>How would you rate the visual of the presentations</p> <p>Excellent</p> <p>Good</p> <p>Satisfaction</p> <p>Poor</p> <p>Very Poor</p>					

3.2.3.2. Summer School Evaluation by the Lecturers

Also, after the trainings the lecturer evaluation surveys were sent to all lecturers and the survey results are as follows:

Questionnaire	
<p>I had enough time to prepare my presentation.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ● Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>	
<p>The time allowed for the training was appropriate.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ● Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>	
<p>The content presented was appropriate to the training objectives.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ● Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>	
<p>The content presented was compatible with students' needs.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ● Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>	
<p>The students were interested and enthusiastic.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ● Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>	
<p>I was able to encourage critical thinking and problem-solving.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ● Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>	

<p>The online training environment met all training needs.</p> <p>Strongly agree	
<p>I received positive feedback from faculty members and students after the training.</p> <p>Strongly agree	
<p>How do you rate the overall organisation of REMODEL Summer School (registration, schedule, communication etc.)</p> <p>Excellent	
<p>How do you rate the overall students' attitudes towards the training</p> <p>Excellent	
<p>How do you rate your overall training experience</p> <p>Excellent	

3.3. Scope of the Third Summer School (Innovative Business Solutions for Food and Beverage Sector in Hospitality – BUU)

The REMODEL Summer School was organized on September 16–17, 2025, and hosted by Bursa Uludağ University, Faculty of Economics and Administrative Sciences, in collaboration with the REMODEL project. The summer school's core agenda was debating new business models, sustainability actions, and EU project opportunities in hospitality and food businesses.

The subjects of the summer school were broad, with a great diversity of themes:

- Innovative ideas in the restaurant industry,
- Business model innovation in the food & beverage sector,
- Segmentation, positioning, and brand management,
- Cost control and profitability,
- Value proposition design,
- EU research and innovation opportunities,
- Widening participation and ERA strengthening,
- Project presentations (REMODEL, VERNE, DIGIFABS, FUSE, Food Educators, Kitchen Adventure, SECreTOUR, etc.),
- Budget planning, project management, and networking.

The two-day summer school brought together academic expertise and industry real-world experience. Day one focused on lectures and workshops on the food and hospitality industries, ranging from business models and branding to profitability and value proposition design. The day also included a panel on restaurant success stories, where practitioners shared best innovative practices.

The second day turned attention to the European level, with presentations by the project coordinator and invited experts on Horizon Europe funding opportunities, ERA engagement, and proposal submission. Presentations of ongoing EU-funded projects were also delivered on this day, with a spotlight on innovative practices in food education, digital innovation, and cultural tourism.

The programme concluded with panels on budgeting, project management, and networking opportunities, so that participants could transform academic knowledge into practice.

3.3.1. Summer School Lecturers and Contents

On the first day, the summer school was initiated with welcome speeches by BUU Research and Development Coordinator Prof. Dr. Esra Karaca and REMODEL Project Coordinator Prof. Dr. Aylin Poroy Arsoy, welcoming the objectives of the REMODEL Summer School and opening doors for two days of scholarly and professional discussion. The session continued with a panel on "Success Stories from the Sector: Innovative Strategies in Restaurants," moderated by Prof. Dr. Yücel Sayılar, where practitioners Onur Özkul (Food and Beyond), Adnan Nar (Giritli Restourant), and Mehmet Ceylan (Ceylan Bakery) shared their entrepreneurial experience and innovative practices. Subsequently, Prof. Dr. Yasemin Şahan presented the LOCALNUTLEG Project, which included research on Mediterranean legumes and nuts transformed into innovative vegetable-based foods. Prof. Dr. Çağatan Taşkın presented two complementary lectures: "Business Model Development in the Food & Beverage Industry" and "Segmentation and Positioning in the Food & Beverage Industry". Assoc. Prof. Dr. Onur Öztürk continued with "Brand Management in the Food & Beverage Industry", discussing how to build successful brands. Prof. Dr. Ahmet Türel and Prof. Dr. Aslı Türel co-presented "Cost Control and Profitability in the Food & Beverage Industry". The afternoon included an interactive Value Proposition Canvas Workshop by Assoc. Prof. Dr. Mehlika Saraç and Dr. Alp Aytaç, and Question and Discussion Session hosted by Prof. Dr. Yakup Selvi.

During the second day, the attention was turned to EU research and project possibilities. Prof. Dr. Aylin Poroy Arsoy provided two sessions: "Horizon Europe and Other EU Current Project Opportunities (2026–2027 Draft Work Programmes)" and "Horizon Europe Proposal Preparation and Application Process". Project presentations were then given: Ciaran O'Hannracháin on REMODEL Project, Juanita Blue on VERNE Project, and Orla Casey giving a series of initiatives (DIGIFABS, FUSE, 3 Kitchens, Food Eco Culture Edu, Waste2Worth, Ethical Food Entrepreneurship). Viktoria Soos showed the FoodEducators Programme, Kitchen Adventure app, and GreenChef game, and Antonella Fresa presented the SECReTOUR Project. The programme concluded with a joint session on "Budgeting, Project Management, and Networking" by Prof. Dr. Aylin Poroy Arsoy, Prof. Dr. Elif Yücel, and Prof. Dr. Yasemin Ertan, which gave the participants hands-on tools to plan, manage, and sustain well-performing EU projects.

3.3.1.1. Mehmet Ceylan - Onur Özkul & Adnan Nar: Moderator Yücel Sayılar

The first session of the summer school was held under the moderation of Prof. Dr. Yücel Sayılar, a faculty member from the Department of Management and Organization at BUU, with the participation of highly successful and renowned entrepreneurs from the food and beverage industry: Onur Özkul, Adnan Nar, and Mehmet Ceylan. This engaging and interesting session featured each speaker sharing their unique experiences with their restaurant ventures. The participants discussed their innovative approaches in the industry and how they overcame challenges to achieve success.

Mehmet Ceylan's "Ceylan Bakery" initiative makes a significant contribution to the healthy living trend in the sector with its gluten-free and healthy products. The bakery not only offers gluten-free products for individuals embracing a healthy lifestyle but also creates a difference with its "one-stop shop" approach. Customers can find not just bakery products but also healthy snacks and food items in one place. Ceylan Bakery promotes healthy eating habits while also providing a convenient shopping experience. This innovative approach forms a success story that combines healthy living and practical shopping.

Onur Özkul's "Food and Beyond" initiative stands out as a perhaps one-of-a-kind example of social entrepreneurship in the world. This special dining event is organized once a week, where the entire revenue from the evening is donated to LÖDER (Lymphoma and Leukemia Children's Health and Education Foundation). By integrating the concept of social responsibility into the restaurant industry, Özkul offers customers not just a delicious meal, but also raises social awareness. This innovation makes a significant impact in the realm of social entrepreneurship, with its unique fundraising model setting an example for others.

Adnan Nar, in his "Giritli Restaurant" creates a difference by blending traditional mezes with modern presentation and adapting traditional Crete cuisine to the present day. The restaurant stands out with its carefully crafted presentations and a rich variety of mezes. Additionally, the restaurant places a strong emphasis on sustainability. By sourcing products from local suppliers and adopting environmentally friendly practices, it not only plays a role in the gastronomic world but also helps increase environmental awareness. Giritli tells a traditional story with high-quality flavors while also showcasing an innovative approach.

Through this content, the following learning outcomes are expected:

- Learn how the concept of social entrepreneurship can be integrated into the restaurant industry.
- Discover how to differentiate by adding innovative touches to traditional flavors.
- Gain insights into how trends like healthy living and gluten-free products can be adapted to restaurant business models.

Relevance for Academics and Industry and Relationship with Innovation:

This session highlights the success of innovative initiatives in the restaurant industry and their social impact. From an academic perspective, in-depth analyses can be made on the applicability of topics such as social responsibility and sustainability in the gastronomy sector. Additionally, research can explore how new trends like healthy living and gluten-free diets can be integrated into the industry. From an industry perspective, such innovative approaches help restaurants stand out in a competitive market, playing a crucial role in brand-building and customer loyalty. Innovation holds great potential not only from a gastronomic perspective but also in terms of social impact.

3.3.1.2. Yasemin Şahan

Prof. Dr. Yasemin Şahan graduated from Uludağ University, Faculty of Agriculture, Department of Food Engineering in 1996, and completed her MSc and PhD at the same institution. She was appointed Associate Professor in 2012 and Professor in 2020. Her research focuses on food chemistry, bioactive compounds, food quality, nanotechnology applications in food science, and the bioaccessibility of nutrients and antioxidants. She has supervised numerous master's and doctoral theses and has authored many national and international publications, book chapters, and patents. Prof. Şahan has contributed to a wide range of research projects and has been actively involved in scientific committees, accreditation boards, and quality commissions within her faculty. With her extensive academic background and ongoing projects, she continues to make significant contributions to the field of food engineering and technology.

Her session titled “LOCALNUTLEG Project Presentation” introduces an EU-funded initiative under PRIMA Horizon 2020 (2021–2024) that focuses on transforming Mediterranean local legumes and nuts (PDO/PGI and autochthonous varieties) into innovative plant-based foods. It highlights the development of plant-based dairy alternatives, flours for bakery and pasta, and ready-to-eat meal formats, while also addressing consumer acceptance across eight countries. The project aims to strengthen the attractiveness of the Mediterranean diet through innovation, tradition, and sustainability.

Through this content, the following learning outcomes are expected:

- Understanding how local varieties and geographic identity create value in product innovation.
- Learning the end-to-end process of plant-based product development.
- Gaining insight into multi-country consumer research and its applications.
- Exploring eco-friendly processing technologies that preserve nutrients and bioactives.
- Recognizing commercialization and exploitation strategies for sustainable market impact.

Relevance for Academics and Industry and Relationship with Innovation:

For Academics LOCALNUTLEG represents an interdisciplinary research design that integrates nutrition science, food processing, and consumer behavior. It provides a model for producing measurable scientific outputs while strengthening the link between research and societal impact. For industry, the project highlights opportunities for differentiation through the integration of local, geographically protected raw materials into menus, bakery, and ready-to-eat products. Insights into consumer expectations and commercialization strategies accelerate market–product alignment and support health-driven innovation in the food service sector.

And for sustainability and innovation, LOCALNUTLEG demonstrates how eco-friendly processes, biodiversity valorization, and short local supply chains can generate both economic and societal benefits. It also contributes to rural employment and strengthens the cultural identity of the Mediterranean lifestyle, offering a replicable model for sustainable food system innovation.

3.3.1.3. Çağatan Taşkın

Prof. Dr. Çağatan Taşkın is a faculty member at BUU, FEAS, Department of Business Administration. After completing his undergraduate studies in Industrial Engineering, he received his master's and doctoral degrees in Business Administration at the same university. Advancing from research assistant to professor, Taşkın specializes in marketing, strategic marketing, and brand management. He has held several administrative positions such as senate member, vocational school director, and vice director of the graduate school, and has been involved in national and international projects. He has published numerous articles, books, and conference papers, and has supervised both doctoral and master's theses. His academic contributions mainly focus on brand equity, consumer behavior, digital marketing, and sustainable business models.

The sessions “Business Model Development in the Food & Beverage Sector” and “Segmentation and Positioning in the Food & Beverage Sector” address two complementary pillars of strategic management in hospitality and food services. Together, they explore how businesses can design effective business models while also defining target markets and positioning strategies to achieve competitiveness and sustainability.

Through this content, the following learning outcomes are expected:

- Understanding the building blocks of a successful business model in the F&B sector.
- Learning how to identify customer segments and align offerings with market expectations.
- Exploring effective positioning strategies for differentiation and brand value creation.
- Linking business model innovation with profitability and long-term competitiveness.
- Gaining practical insights into applying academic frameworks to real-world food and hospitality cases.

Relevance for Academics and Industry and Relationship with Innovation:

For academics and researchers, these sessions offer a structured framework to study how business models, segmentation, and positioning shape competitiveness in the food and hospitality sector. They highlight the interplay between consumer behavior, strategic design, and market differentiation, providing opportunities for applied research, case study development, and cross-disciplinary collaboration in marketing, entrepreneurship, and innovation studies. For industry professionals, the sessions translate abstract concepts into actionable strategies. Business model development helps entrepreneurs and managers design value creation, delivery, and capture mechanisms tailored to evolving consumer expectations. Segmentation and positioning provide the tools to identify niche markets, respond to demographic and lifestyle trends, and craft distinctive brand identities.

From an innovation perspective, combining business model design with segmentation enables firms to adapt quickly to shifts in consumer demand, integrate digital technologies, and experiment with new service formats. This alignment supports resilience in a competitive market, fosters sustainable growth, and strengthens the sector's ability to create differentiated, innovative offerings that appeal to diverse audiences.

3.3.1.4. Onur Öztürk

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Onur Öztürk is a faculty member at BUU FEAS, Department of Business Administration. He completed his undergraduate studies in Business Administration at Ege University, also studying at Vilnius Gediminas Technical University in Lithuania, and pursued his master's degree in Business Administration at BUU. Specializing in marketing, he has served in academic positions from research assistant to associate professor. Öztürk has published numerous articles in peer-reviewed journals, authored several books on topics such as digital marketing, social media, and tourism applications, and presented papers at international conferences. His research mainly focuses on online service quality, consumer behavior, brand equity, and the impact of digitalization on marketing. He has also contributed to international projects supported by the EU, strengthening research capacity in innovative business models for the hospitality sector.

The session titled “Brand Management in the Food & Beverage Sector” focuses on the principles, strategies, and challenges of building and sustaining strong brands in hospitality and food services. It examines how branding goes beyond logos and names, influencing consumer perception, loyalty, and market differentiation. The session also highlights case examples and frameworks relevant to managing brand equity in competitive and rapidly evolving markets.

Through this content, the following learning outcomes are expected:

- Understanding the fundamentals of brand identity, image, and equity.
- Learning how to create and sustain brand value in the F&B sector.
- Exploring strategies for brand positioning and differentiation in crowded markets.
- Gaining insights into consumer-brand relationships and loyalty mechanisms.
- Recognizing the role of innovation in maintaining brand relevance and resilience.

Relevance for Academics and Industry and Relationship with Innovation

For academics, this session provides conceptual and analytical tools to study how brands influence consumer decision-making and business performance. It also offers opportunities for case study development and applied research in hospitality branding.

For industry professionals, the session translates branding theory into practical strategies for creating distinctive customer experiences, building trust, and enhancing competitiveness. Strong brand management supports innovation by enabling businesses to introduce new products, expand into new markets, and adapt to changing consumer trends without losing credibility.

Ultimately, brand management acts as a bridge between innovation and consumer acceptance, ensuring that creative business models and new offerings are effectively communicated, embraced, and sustained in the food and hospitality industry.

3.3.1.5. Ahmet Türel & Aslı Türel

Prof. Dr. Ahmet Türel is a professor at Istanbul University, Faculty of Business Administration. He earned his bachelor's, master's, and doctoral degrees at Istanbul University and also completed a master's degree at Ball State University in the United States. Specializing in accounting, financial reporting, and auditing, he advanced from research assistant to professor while also serving in several administrative roles, including vice dean. His work, published in international journals, books, and conference proceedings, has contributed to the understanding of audit quality, financial reporting, and corporate governance. He has also served as researcher in numerous national and international projects, providing significant input to studies in accounting and finance.

Prof. Dr. Aslı Türel is a professor at Istanbul University, Faculty of Business Administration, specializing in accounting and auditing. She completed her bachelor's, master's, and doctoral studies at the same university and has held several academic and administrative positions, including vice director of the Institute of Accounting, vice chair of the department, and vice dean. Her research focuses on international financial reporting, audit quality, and independent auditing. With numerous national and international publications, she has also taken part in various research projects, including EU-funded initiatives, contributing significantly to the field of accounting and auditing

Their session titled “Cost Control and Profitability in the Food & Beverage Sector” examines the financial dimension of managing hospitality and food businesses. It focuses on strategies for monitoring costs, optimizing resource use, and ensuring profitability in a competitive environment. Special attention is given to the relationship between cost structures, pricing strategies, and value creation, providing participants with tools to balance efficiency and innovation.

Through this content, the following learning outcomes are expected:

- Understanding the fundamentals of cost structures and financial management in F&B.
- Learning techniques for cost control and efficiency improvement.
- Exploring approaches to link pricing, profitability, and customer value.
- Gaining insights into financial decision-making and risk management.
- Recognizing how financial sustainability underpins business innovation and growth.

Relevance for Academics and Industry and Relationship with Innovation:

For academics, this session enriches the study of hospitality economics and financial management, offering models and frameworks that can be applied in research and teaching. It highlights the interplay between financial sustainability and innovation, opening avenues for interdisciplinary inquiry.

For industry professionals, cost control and profitability are practical imperatives. The session equips managers and entrepreneurs with actionable strategies to manage expenses, improve margins, and enhance competitiveness without compromising service quality.

From an innovation perspective, strong financial management ensures that businesses can invest in new technologies, adopt sustainable practices, and experiment with novel service models. By aligning cost efficiency with value creation, the session demonstrates how financial discipline becomes a driver of long-term innovation, resilience, and sustainable growth in the hospitality and food sectors.

3.3.1.6. Mehlika Saraç & Alp Aytac

Dr. Mehlika Saraç is an Associate Professor at the Department of Business Administration, BUU. She holds a PhD in Management and Organizational Sciences from BUU. She is teaching on organizational behavior, social entrepreneurship, sustainable business models, and business innovation. She actively contributes to EU-funded projects focusing on business innovation, sustainable transformation and policy recommendations for SMEs, especially within the hospitality sector.

Dr. Aytac has been working as an Assistant Professor at BUU since 2022. He started the academia at 2013 as a Research Assistant. He completed his undergraduate, master's degree and PhD at the BUU as well. He has published several articles on various journals. He mainly publishes articles related with auditing, sustainability and internal control. He has been giving lectures in Turkish and English. He also an active researcher in European Union funded projects. Apart from his academic career, he is also board member of the Association of Accounting and Finance Academicians (MUFAD).

In this workshop, Mehlika Saraç and Alp Aytac moderated a session where participants were introduced to the fundamentals of innovative business models and the value proposition canvas. Participants then worked in teams to create imaginary businesses, identifying customer segments, the value they offer, and how they differentiate from competitors, and prepared value proposition canvases for each business. The teams deepened their business models and presented creative business ideas and innovative solutions, gaining firsthand experience in how the value proposition canvas works and how innovative business models are designed. This process provided participants with significant theoretical and practical insights.

Through this content, the following learning outcomes are expected:

- Learn the key components of the value proposition canvas and how to apply them.
- Gain insights into the design of innovative business models.
- Understand how to develop customer-centric business strategies and create value propositions.
- Create and present a value proposition canvas for an imaginary business through practical application.

Relevance for Academics and Industry and Relationship with Innovation:

This workshop demonstrated how businesses can design innovative models and use the value proposition canvas as an effective tool. From an academic perspective, such workshops provide students with a concrete understanding of business strategies and innovation processes. For the industry, the value proposition creation process offers entrepreneurs a practical roadmap for standing out in competitive markets, building brand identity, and customer loyalty. This workshop strengthened participants' abilities to think innovatively and develop applied strategies.

3.3.1.7. Aylin Poroy Arsoy

Prof. Aylin Poroy Arsoy is a professor of accounting and finance at Bursa Uludağ University. Her research interests include financial reporting, corporate transparency, sustainability reporting, integrated reporting, accounting education, and auditing. She has coordinated and participated in numerous national and EU-funded projects (e.g., Horizon Europe, Erasmus+), focusing on innovative business models, academic hospitality, and financial control systems. She has published widely in international journals and contributed to several book chapters. Prof. Poroy Arsoy is open to collaborative research, especially on interdisciplinary projects that intersect accounting, governance, and sustainability in both academic and practical contexts. She is interested in "Social Sciences and Humanities, Accounting, Accounting and Control, Management of Enterprises".

The sessions "Horizon Europe and Other EU Current Funding and Project Opportunities (2026–2027 Draft Work Programmes)" and "Widening Participation and Strengthening the European Research Area (ERA)" together provide a comprehensive overview of the EU's research and innovation funding landscape. Prof. Dr. Aylin Poroy Arsoy presents both the broad opportunities of Horizon Europe and the special instruments designed for widening countries such as Türkiye. The first part highlights the architecture of Horizon Europe, including its three main pillars and cross-cutting components, project types (RIA, IA, CSA, Co-Fund), and the draft priorities of the 2026–2027 work programmes across clusters such as health, culture, security, digitalization, climate, mobility, and food systems. The second part focuses on Widening and ERA measures, which aim to reduce disparities in research capacity by funding initiatives like twinning, teaming, excellence hubs, and ERA chairs, fostering collaboration and inclusion in EU research.

Through this content, the following learning outcomes are expected:

- Understanding the pillars, instruments, and funding schemes of Horizon Europe.
- Differentiating between bottom-up and top-down calls and applying this knowledge to proposal design.
- Exploring the 2026–2027 draft priorities and their relevance for research and industry.
- Recognizing the mechanisms of Widening and ERA actions and their role in strengthening institutional capacity.
- Identifying concrete opportunities for Turkish universities, SMEs, and research centers to increase participation and competitiveness in EU programmes.

Relevance for Academics and Industry and Relationship with Innovation:

For academics, these combined sessions provide a strategic roadmap for navigating EU research programmes, building international networks, and improving competitiveness in proposal writing. They emphasize how widening instruments can help institutions in Türkiye integrate into Europe's research ecosystem while boosting publication and innovation capacity. For industry, Horizon Europe and widening actions create entry points into EU innovation ecosystems, enabling SMEs and entrepreneurs to access funding, scale new technologies, and collaborate with academic and public partners. By combining mainstream Horizon calls with widening-targeted actions, businesses and universities can co-develop projects that balance excellence with inclusiveness. From an innovation perspective, the sessions show how Horizon Europe serves as a driver of scientific and technological excellence, while widening and ERA measures ensure that excellence is more evenly spread across Europe. Together, they foster inclusive, competitive, and resilient innovation ecosystems, with Türkiye playing an active role in shaping Europe's research and innovation future.

3.3.1.8. Juanita Blue

Juanita Blue is ATU's Senior European Project Officer. She has Extensive experience as a Programme Manager, leader and managing European funded projects under Horizon, Interreg, and Erasmus+. She advises researchers how to successfully access EU funding, and how to manage awarded projects. She also manages various EU funded projects across multiple disciplines on behalf of ATU. She holds a B.Sc. (hons) in Computer Security & Digital Forensics. As part of her ongoing Ph.D., she has conducted extensive research in the areas of Intelligent Identity Authentication and Intelligent Agents. Her work has been disseminated at forums both nationally and internationally. Juanita is an accomplished lecturer in the areas of Computer Security; Risk, Governance & Compliance; Biometrics; and Maths for Cryptography.

The session titled “VERNE Project Presentation” introduces a European initiative that seeks to accelerate the transition of local and regional tourist destinations toward sustainable and circular models. VERNE redefines sustainable tourism by integrating circular economy principles to minimize waste, reduce energy use, and protect ecosystems, while fostering collaboration across mobility, food, construction, and waste management sectors.

Through this content, the following learning outcomes are expected:

- Understanding the mission and framework of the VERNE project.
- Learning how circular economy practices can be applied to tourism and hospitality.
- Exploring strategies for engaging diverse stakeholders—industry, policymakers, communities, and tourists—in co-developing solutions.
- Gaining insights into pilot projects (waste management, food waste reduction, wastewater treatment, e-mobility, and digital tools) that demonstrate scalable models.
- Recognizing how new business models can link competitiveness and sustainability in tourism.

Relevance for Academics and Industry and Relationship with Innovation:

For academics, VERNE offers a multidimensional framework to study how circular economy principles intersect with tourism innovation, opening avenues for interdisciplinary research and policy analysis. It highlights how sustainability can be embedded into destination management, business models, and consumer behavior.

For industry stakeholders, the project provides practical, evidence-based approaches to implement resource-efficient, eco-friendly, and community-driven practices. The pilots showcase how innovations such as digital solutions, electric mobility, and circular waste systems can strengthen competitiveness while reducing environmental impact.

By bridging academia, policy, and industry, VERNE demonstrates how tourism can evolve into a driver of sustainable innovation, contributing simultaneously to local well-being, economic resilience, and environmental protection.

3.3.1.9. Ciarán Ó'hannracháin

Dr. Ciarán Ó'hannracháin is a Faculty of Business Strategic Projects Manager at ATU with a focus on Research & Collaboration Projects and holds the Operational Board Chair of the World Technology Universities Network (WTUN), a global network of universities focused on delivering on the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Previous roles include Project Manager of Academic Planning and Strategy, Internationalisation and External Engagement during the creation of ATU. Ciarán has also held Senior Academic Management positions in the Irish, UK, US and Swiss education systems, and lectures in Hospitality and Tourism Management. His research interests include both Education and Business.

The session titled “REMODEL Project Presentation” introduces a three-year Horizon project funded under HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ACCESS-03-01, which focuses on Strengthening the Research Capacity of Turkey in Innovative Business Models for the Hospitality Sector. Coordinated by Bursa Uludağ University in collaboration with Universidad de León (Spain) and Atlantic Technological University (Ireland), the project aims to enhance R&I capacity, foster knowledge transfer, and design innovative business models for SMEs in the Turkish hospitality sector.

Through this content, the following learning outcomes are expected:

- Understanding the mission and vision of the REMODEL project to strengthen academic and industry research capacity.
- Gaining insights into the creation and role of the Business Model Innovation Laboratory.
- Learning how consumer behavior analysis, neuromarketing, and entrepreneurship tools contribute to innovative business models.
- Exploring strategies for staff exchanges, training programmes, and summer schools that enhance international collaboration.
- Recognizing the impact of REMODEL on both academic publishing capacity and SME competitiveness in the hospitality sector.

Relevance for Academics and Industry and Relationship with Innovation:

For academics, REMODEL provides a platform for long-term scientific strategy, joint R&I programmes, and capacity building in business model innovation. It strengthens the research and publication profile of Bursa Uludağ University, while fostering collaboration with European institutions and preparing the ground for international master's programmes in hospitality management. For industry stakeholders, REMODEL directly supports SME innovation and competitiveness by designing and testing novel business models that respond to the challenges of the post-COVID-19 era. The BMI Lab offers practical tools for integrating consumer insights, sustainability, and leadership practices into everyday business operations.

From an innovation perspective, REMODEL demonstrates how academic–industry collaboration, training, and applied research can build resilience, sustainability, and global competitiveness in the hospitality sector. It showcases how innovative business models can contribute not only to firm-level performance but also to the sustainability and growth of the national economy

3.3.1.10. Orla Casey

Founder of Momentum in 2003, Orla is a business graduate who completed further studies in the areas of European Law and Economics and Marketing. She is a sought-after researcher and facilitator, regeneration specialist and application writer. Working with public and private organisations, Orla brings a clarity of thought and direction to the design and delivery of multi-million regenerative economy strategies and initiatives in Ireland. Orla has proudly supported The Food Hub consistently over almost 20 years of growth. Orla is very passionate about the transfer of innovation between Ireland and Europe. Over the years, she has built strategic alliances with European leaders in adult, youth, VET and higher education.

The session demystifies how to win EU funding by breaking it into a practical formula—aligning your ideas, skills, and networks with EU priorities—and by showing what evaluators look for in competitive proposals. It maps real entry pathways (start with Erasmus+ Cooperation Partnerships, then scale to Horizon/ESF+), explains success criteria (relevance, partnership quality, the “golden thread,” impact & sustainability), and illustrates each point with live project cases in food, hospitality, and sustainability

Through this content, the following learning outcomes are expected:

- Understanding the EU funding landscape and Türkiye’s access across Horizon, Erasmus+, and related programmes.
- Learning a step-by-step pathway from first Erasmus+ projects to larger Horizon/ESF+ consortia, and why “start small, then scale” works.
- Mastering what assessors score: Relevance (need & evidence), Partnership fit, Quality of design and Impact/Dissemination/Sustainability.
- Applying partner selection rules (role–CV match, sector balance, red flags to avoid) and designing proportionate, credible work packages.
- Seeing concrete deliverable models (living labs, competence frameworks, OER toolkits, bootcamps) through cases like Food Eco Culture Edu, EcoSmart Hospitality, 3 Kitchens, Waste2Worth, Ethical Food Entrepreneurship, DIGIFABS, and FUSE.

Relevance for Academics and Industry and Relationship with Innovation

For academics and researchers, the session offers a replicable blueprint for competitive proposals—how to evidence needs, thread objectives to impacts, and embed outputs (curricula, living labs, OERs) so projects outlive the grant. It also shows how early Erasmus+ wins can build reputation, publications, and invitations to Horizon consortia. For industry, SMEs, NGOs, and public bodies, it translates funding language into actionable project architectures—digital/green competence frameworks for hospitality (EcoSmart Hospitality), circular food-waste toolkits (Waste2Worth), and workforce & inclusion pathways (3 Kitchens; FUSE). These examples demonstrate how partners co-create resources that improve skills, resilience, and market readiness.

From an innovation perspective, the showcased projects model cross-sector collaboration (universities–VET–SMEs–authorities) to deliver scalable, sustainable solutions from training bootcamps and summer schools (DIGIFABS) to ethical entrepreneurship curricula aligned with the SDGs (Ethical Food Entrepreneurship). The emphasis on measurable impact and replication makes innovation systematic rather than accidental.

3.3.1.11. Viktoria Soos

Viktoria Soos is a seasoned professional with extensive experience in communication and coaching. As the Founder and Communications Expert at Climate Smart Elephant since January 2019, Viktoria has also served as the Communication Lead for EIT Food and as a Communication Specialist for URBACT since 2019. Additionally, Viktoria is a Communication Strategist for Hegyvidéki Zöld Iroda, focusing on sustainability initiatives in Budapest. With a background in personal development and business coaching since 2009, Viktoria has facilitated numerous trainings and events. Educational qualifications include a Master's degree in American Literature from Debreceni Egyetem, a Master's in Psychology from Károli Gáspár Református Egyetem, and a degree in Gender Studies from Central European University.

The session titled “Food Education and Gamified Sustainability Tools” presents innovative approaches to linking food, biodiversity, sustainability, and education through communication strategies and digital solutions. Viktoria Soos, psychologist and sustainability communication expert at Climate Smart Elephant, introduces flagship initiatives such as the FoodEducators Programme, Kitchen Adventure app, EcoQuest digital platform, and Green Chef card game. Together, these initiatives highlight how education, behavior change, and gamification can foster healthier food choices and stronger sustainability awareness across Europe.

Through this content, the following learning outcomes are expected:

- Understanding how food education programmes operate at European and national levels, including lesson plans, career days, and international school networks .
- Learning how gamification and digital tools (Kitchen Adventure, EcoQuest) promote plant-forward diets, behavioral change, and youth engagement.
- Exploring how to design communication strategies that integrate sustainability with marketing and education.
- Gaining insights into how cross-country partnerships and Erasmus/EIT-Food projects create scalable and multilingual learning resources.
- Recognizing how tools like the Green Chef card game can improve culinary education and sustainability awareness in vocational education and training (VET).

Relevance for Academics and Industry and Relationship with Innovation:

For academics, the session showcases how interdisciplinary research and education design can translate into practical outputs for schools, VET institutions, and digital platforms. It also provides a model for embedding behavioral science, psychology, and sustainability studies into applied EU projects. For industry and the hospitality sector, these tools offer ready-to-use resources to train staff, engage communities, and promote sustainable practices in food services. By leveraging gamification, AI-based assistants, and digital communication, businesses can enhance consumer awareness, support healthier choices, and strengthen brand identity around sustainability.

From an innovation perspective, these projects illustrate how communication, education, and digital design can converge to build impactful solutions for the food system. They demonstrate how sustainability can be gamified, personalized, and scaled, ensuring long-term engagement and measurable behavior change.

3.3.1.12. Antonella Fresa

Antonella Fresa is an ICT expert with extensive experience in European cooperation projects since 1994. She has served as Design Director and General Manager at Promoter srl, and held roles as Technical Coordinator and Communication-Dissemination Manager in numerous European Commission projects. Between 1999 and 2002, she worked as a Project Officer at the European Commission and later advised the Italian Ministry of Cultural Heritage. As an Enterprise Fellow at Coventry University, she contributes to European projects in social sciences, humanities, cultural heritage, and technological innovation. She is Vice-President of PHOTOCONSORTIUM – the International Consortium for Photographic Heritage – and a founding member of IDEA. Fresa is recognized as a leading figure in the fields of digitisation, preservation, and innovative use of technology for cultural heritage.

The session titled “Cultural Tourism: Bridging Heritage, Places and Communities” examines the transformative potential of cultural tourism in Europe. It highlights both opportunities and risks: while heritage offers enormous value for identity and local economies, overtourism and commercialization can threaten landscapes and communities. The presentation explores new cultural business models, heritage communities, and EU-funded projects such as SECReTOUR, which experiment with sustainable and inclusive approaches to tourism.

Through this content, the following learning outcomes are expected:

- Understanding the economic and social potential of cultural tourism as a driver of local development.
- Recognizing the negative impacts of overexploitation (overtourism, gentrification, commodification) and strategies to counteract them.
- Learning how tourism can act as a tool for regeneration, community recognition, and rediscovery of shared resources.
- Exploring heritage communities as agents of sustainability and how operational methods can integrate them into territorial governance.
- Gaining insights from pilot projects across Europe that test innovative approaches in rural landscapes, minority heritages, dark heritage, and digital nomadism.

Relevance for Academics and Industry and Relationship with Innovation

For academics, the session provides an interdisciplinary framework linking cultural heritage studies, sustainable tourism research, and digital transformation. It offers concrete examples of how EU-funded projects (e.g., MEMOLA, REACH, INCULTUM, SECReTOUR) generate new research agendas and policy insights on cultural tourism.

For industry professionals and policymakers, the session demonstrates how place-based, historically rooted business models can create value while preserving identity. It shows practical ways to align tourism with sustainability by engaging communities, fostering fair business models, and leveraging digital tools for heritage digitization and promotion.

From an innovation perspective, cultural tourism emerges as a field where digital technologies, participatory governance, and heritage management converge. By designing new cultural business models—complex, collaborative, and rooted in local history—the sector can strengthen resilience, inclusivity, and long-term sustainability.

3.2.2. Participants

The REMODEL summer school organized by BUU received significant interest from academics, researchers, and practitioners. There was a great interest in the summer school. Totaly 93 participants continued the summer school and got their certificates. Some Information about the participants from project partner countries and different professional groups is as follows:

Country	Number of Participants
<i>Hungary</i>	1
<i>Ireland</i>	3
<i>Italy</i>	1
<i>Türkiye</i>	88
Total	93

Professional Categories	Number of Participants
<i>Hospitality Sector Practitioner</i>	13
<i>Academics /Researcher</i>	56
<i>Student</i>	24
Total	93

Professional Categories	Number of Participants
<i>Female</i>	58
<i>Male</i>	35
Total	93

In the workshop conducted by Assoc. Prof. Dr. Mehlika Saraç, the participants are working in teams to prepare a value proposition canvas.

"The summer school attracted great interest from the participants."

3.3.3. Summer School Evaluation

Summer school evaluation forms were prepared for both participants and speakers to assess the training provided during the summer school. At the end of the session, the forms were sent online to both participants and speakers.

3.3.3.1. Summer School Evaluation by the Participants

After the summer school was completed, evaluation forms were sent to all participants. 20 participants took part in the evaluation regarding the summer school. The participants' assessments are as follows:

Questionnaire							
<p>The agenda of the summer school was satisfactory.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ● Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>	<table border="1"> <caption>Data for 'The agenda of the summer school was satisfactory.'</caption> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Strongly agree</td> <td>83.3%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Agree</td> <td>16.7%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Percentage	Strongly agree	83.3%	Agree	16.7%
Response	Percentage						
Strongly agree	83.3%						
Agree	16.7%						
<p>The lecturers were knowledgeable about the training topics.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ● Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>	<table border="1"> <caption>Data for 'The lecturers were knowledgeable about the training topics.'</caption> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Strongly agree</td> <td>75%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Agree</td> <td>25%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Percentage	Strongly agree	75%	Agree	25%
Response	Percentage						
Strongly agree	75%						
Agree	25%						

<p>The lecturers were well prepared.</p> <p>Strongly agree	
<p>The contents were well-organised and easy to follow.</p> <p>Strongly agree	
<p>The lecturers provided interesting examples from their experiences.</p> <p>Strongly agree	
<p>I consider the expertise of the lecturers:</p> <p>Very High	
<p>The time allocated for the summer school was sufficient.</p> <p>Strongly agree	
<p>The training contents met my expectations.</p> <p>Strongly agree	
<p>Participation and interaction were encouraged.</p> <p>Strongly agree	

<p>This training experience will be useful in my work.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ● Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Strongly agree</td> <td>50%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Agree</td> <td>31.3%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Neutral</td> <td>18.8%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Percentage	Strongly agree	50%	Agree	31.3%	Neutral	18.8%
Response	Percentage								
Strongly agree	50%								
Agree	31.3%								
Neutral	18.8%								
<p>The learning environment met all training needs.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ● Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Strongly agree</td> <td>50%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Agree</td> <td>50%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Percentage	Strongly agree	50%	Agree	50%		
Response	Percentage								
Strongly agree	50%								
Agree	50%								
<p>I would recommend REMODEL summer school to other people.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ● Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Strongly agree</td> <td>62.5%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Agree</td> <td>37.5%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Percentage	Strongly agree	62.5%	Agree	37.5%		
Response	Percentage								
Strongly agree	62.5%								
Agree	37.5%								
<p>How would you rate the overall organisation of REMODEL summer school (registration, schedule, organisation etc.)</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ● Satisfaction ● Poor ● Very Poor ●</p>	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Excellent</td> <td>75%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Good</td> <td>25%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Percentage	Excellent	75%	Good	25%		
Response	Percentage								
Excellent	75%								
Good	25%								
<p>How would you rate the visual of the presentations</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ● Satisfaction ● Poor ● Very Poor ●</p>	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Excellent</td> <td>50%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Good</td> <td>43.8%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Satisfaction</td> <td>6.2%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Percentage	Excellent	50%	Good	43.8%	Satisfaction	6.2%
Response	Percentage								
Excellent	50%								
Good	43.8%								
Satisfaction	6.2%								
<p>How do you rate the quality of presentations</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ● Satisfaction ● Poor ● Very Poor ●</p>	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Excellent</td> <td>50%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Good</td> <td>50%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Percentage	Excellent	50%	Good	50%		
Response	Percentage								
Excellent	50%								
Good	50%								
<p>How would you rate the quality of the lecturers</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ● Satisfaction ● Poor ● Very Poor ●</p>	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Excellent</td> <td>50%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Good</td> <td>50%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Percentage	Excellent	50%	Good	50%		
Response	Percentage								
Excellent	50%								
Good	50%								

3.1.3.2. Summer School Evaluation by the Lecturers

Also, after the summer school the lecturer evaluation surveys were sent to all lecturers and the survey results are as follows:

Questionnaire	First Day
<p>I had enough time to prepare my presentation.</p> <p>Strongly agree	
<p>The time allowed for the training was appropriate.</p> <p>Strongly agree	
<p>The content presented was appropriate to the training objectives.</p> <p>Strongly agree	
<p>The content presented was compatible with students' needs.</p> <p>Strongly agree	
<p>The students were interested and enthusiastic.</p> <p>Strongly agree	
<p>I was able to encourage critical thinking and problem-solving.</p> <p>Strongly agree	

<p>The online training environment met all training needs.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ● Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Strongly agree</td> <td>85.7%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Agree</td> <td>14.3%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Percentage	Strongly agree	85.7%	Agree	14.3%		
Response	Percentage								
Strongly agree	85.7%								
Agree	14.3%								
<p>I received positive feedback from faculty members and students after the training.</p> <p>Strongly agree ● Agree ● Neutral ● Disagree ● Strongly disagree ●</p>	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Strongly agree</td> <td>85.7%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Agree</td> <td>14.3%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Percentage	Strongly agree	85.7%	Agree	14.3%		
Response	Percentage								
Strongly agree	85.7%								
Agree	14.3%								
<p>How do you rate the overall organisation of REMODEL summer school (registration, schedule, communication etc.)</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ● Satisfaction ● Poor ● Very poor ●</p>	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Excellent</td> <td>85.7%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Good</td> <td>14.3%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Percentage	Excellent	85.7%	Good	14.3%		
Response	Percentage								
Excellent	85.7%								
Good	14.3%								
<p>How do you rate the overall students' attitudes towards the training</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ● Satisfaction ● Poor ● Very poor ●</p>	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Excellent</td> <td>71.4%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Good</td> <td>14.3%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Satisfaction</td> <td>14.3%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Percentage	Excellent	71.4%	Good	14.3%	Satisfaction	14.3%
Response	Percentage								
Excellent	71.4%								
Good	14.3%								
Satisfaction	14.3%								
<p>How do you rate your overall training experience</p> <p>Excellent ● Good ● Satisfaction ● Poor ● Very poor ●</p>	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Excellent</td> <td>71.4%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Good</td> <td>28.6%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Percentage	Excellent	71.4%	Good	28.6%		
Response	Percentage								
Excellent	71.4%								
Good	28.6%								

ANNEX 1. Visiting Lecturer Leaflets

VISITING LECTURE

REMODEL Visiting Lecture
for Bursa Uludag University PhD Students

Funded by
the European Union

April 26th, 2023
 Time: 10:00 - 12:00

 Hosted by The Management
Organization PhD Class

 BUU Faculty of Economics and
Administrative Sciences
Dean Classroom (2. Floor)

Embedding Trust in Our Interpersonal and Inter-Organisational Actions

- What is Trust?
- Advantages/Disadvantages of Trust
- Barriers and Enablers of Trust Development
- Fragility of Trust

Atlantic
Technological
University

Visiting Professor:
Dr. Conor McTernan

April 27th, 2023
 Time: 10:00 - 12:00

 Hosted by The Business
Administration PhD Class

 BUU Faculty of Economics and
Administrative Sciences
Dean Classroom (2. Floor)

The Importance of Proactive Knowledge Management in Contemporary Organisations

- What is Knowledge Management
- Types of Knowledge - Tacit and Explicit
- Sources of Knowledge
- The Challenge of Codifying Tacit Knowledge
- Absorptive Capacity, Competitive Advantage and Organisational Effectiveness

Courses are open to the participation of all PhD students registered in Bursa Uludag University Social Sciences Institute. Certificates of participants will be provided to PhD students who attend the courses. Please fill in the form for registration.

Visit Our Website:
www.projectremodel.eu

REGISTRATION LINK

VISITING LECTURE

REMODEL Visiting Lecture
for Bursa Uludag University PhD Students

Funded by
the European Union

October 4th, 2023
 Time: 13:30 - 16:00

 BUU Faculty of Economics
Administration Sciences

Navigating Governance, Ethics and Sustainability

- The role and responsibilities of the board of directors in corporate governance
- How the composition of a board can affect its operation?
- The main elements of corporate social responsibility, stakeholder theory, ethics, and sustainability
- Trends in governance, ethics and sustainability

Atlantic
Technological
University

Visiting Professor:
Dr. Anne Burke

October 5th, 2023
 Time: 13:30 - 16:00

 BUU Faculty of Economics
Administration Sciences

Unravelling Organisational Culture

- The common characteristics of organisational culture
- How culture is transmitted to employees?
- The factors that create and sustain an organization's culture
- The functional and dysfunctional effects of organizational culture on people and the organization

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Visit Our Website:
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VISITING LECTURE

REMODEL Visiting Lecture
for Bursa Uludag University PhD Students

Funded by
the European Union

February 22nd, 2024
Time: 09:30 - 12:45

BUU Faculty of Economics
and Administrative Sciences

MATLAB for Validating Hypotheses When Working with Datasets

- What is Matlab?
- Matlab Tool for Papers Based on Datasets
- Knowing Matlab: Mathematical operations, commands scripts, functions, and graphical representation.
- Machine Learning and Statics
- Matlab with ChatGPT

Description

This workshop aims to provide students basic Matlab knowledge. Thank to this tool the researchers will be able to work with complex datasets in order to develop statistical treatment and machine learning models. This workshop will be a first approach to this programming language, so the students will know the basic primitives understanding the automatic outputs of new AI tools such as ChatGPT.

Coursework

- Matlab with Fuzzy Logic Toolbox
- Matlab with Statistics and Machine Learning Toolbox
- PowerPoint Presentations
- Practical Examples
- ChatGPT 3.5 Free Version Better 4.0

Visiting Professor:
Héctor Alaiz Moretón

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Please fill in the form for registration

Visit Our Website:
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VISITING LECTURE

REMODEL Visiting Lecture
for Bursa Uludag University PhD Students

Funded by
the European Union

February 21st, 2024
Time: 09:30 - 12:45

BUU Faculty of Economics
and Administrative Sciences

Unleashing the Power of ChatGPT: Revolutionizing Education, Research, and Management for Enhanced Productivity

- Understand the Foundational Principles and Technology Behind ChatGPT
- Explore Innovative Ways to Incorporate ChatGPT in Teaching Methodologies and Classroom Activities
- Discover How ChatGPT Can Assist in Various Stages of Research, From Literature Review to Data Analysis
- Learn to Leverage ChatGPT for Effective Management and Administrative Tasks, Enhancing Efficiency
- Identify Best Practices for Integrating ChatGPT into Your Workflow to Maximize Productivity and Innovation
- Discuss Ethical Considerations and Limitations of Using AI Tools Like ChatGPT in Professional Settings
- Engage in Practical Exercises to Experience First-Hand the Capabilities of ChatGPT
- Develop Strategies for Staying Abreast of Evolving AI Technologies and Their Applications in Your Field

Description

This workshop delves into the groundbreaking world of ChatGPT, offering a comprehensive overview of its capabilities and applications in education, research, and management. Participants will explore how ChatGPT can be harnessed as a powerful tool to augment productivity, enhance learning experiences, and streamline research and administrative processes. The session aims to demystify the technology behind ChatGPT, illustrating its potential to transform various professional landscapes. Join us to embark on a journey through the innovative uses of ChatGPT and discover strategies to integrate this advanced AI into your daily operations.

Coursework

Participants will engage in hands-on activities where they will apply ChatGPT to specific scenarios in teaching, research, and management. These activities will include crafting lesson plans, simulating research tasks, and managing hypothetical administrative challenges.

Visiting Professor:
José Alberto Benítez Andrade

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VISITING LECTURE

REMODEL Visiting Lecture
for Bursa Uludag University PhD Students

Funded by
the European Union

May 8th, 2024
Time: 09:30 - 12:30

BUU Faculty of Economics
and Administrative Sciences

Neuromarketing Briefing and Eye-Tracking Insights

- Understanding the key sections that a neuromarketing briefing should include for effective project management with companies
- Understanding the concept of eye-tracking and what it measures.
- Being able to conduct an online eye-tracking study and draw relevant conclusions leading to business implications.

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Visiting Lecturer:
Aroa Costa Feito

Courses are open to the participation of all PhD students registered in Bursa Uludağ University Social Sciences Institute. Certificates of participants will be provided to PhD students who attend the courses. Please fill in the form for registration.

Visit Our Website:

www.projectremodel.eu

VISITING LECTURE

REMODEL Visiting Lecture
for Bursa Uludag University PhD Students

Funded by
the European Union

May 9th, 2024
Time: 09:30 - 12:30

BUU Faculty of Economics
and Administrative Sciences

Web Scraping Fundamentals for Structured Data

- Understand what web scraping is, and differentiate between web crawler and web scraper.
- To know the main free and paid tools for web scraping.
- How to download data from tourist platforms like Tripadvisor.
- How to download data from social media platforms like Instagram or Twitter.

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Visiting Lecturer:
Sofia Blanco-Moreno

Courses are open to the participation of all PhD students registered in Bursa Uludağ University Social Sciences Institute. Certificates of participants will be provided to PhD students who attend the courses. Please fill in the form for registration.

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VISITING LECTURE

REMODEL Visiting Lecture
for Bursa Uludag University PhD Students

Funded by
the European Union

May 15th, 2024
Time: 13:00 - 16:00

BUU Faculty of Economics
and Administrative Sciences

Creative Entrepreneurship – Exploring Lived Experience

- Explore theoretical and practical issues relating to entrepreneurial opportunity.
- Identify the characteristics of creative industry entrepreneurs.
- Discuss the benefits and challenges of conducting qualitative research.
- Critique the use of interviews as a data collection method

Visiting Lecturer:
Tena Patten

Courses are open to the participation of all PhD students registered in Bursa Uludag University Social Sciences Institute. Certificates of participants will be provided to PhD students who attend the courses. Please fill in the form for registration.

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VISITING LECTURE

REMODEL Visiting Lecture
for Bursa Uludag University PhD Students

Funded by
the European Union

November 7th - 8th, 2024
Time: 09:30 - 12:30

BUU Faculty of Economics
and Administrative Sciences

Designing and Conducting Quantitative Research

Learning Outcomes

- Develop a conceptual framework with an appropriate research protocol
- Explore the different options for quantitative research methods
- Understand the challenges in quantitative research design
- Explain the concepts of reliability and validity

Description

In this workshop, participants will learn how to develop a conceptual framework with an appropriate research protocol, design appropriate surveys, and implement effective measurement techniques. The workshop will cover the fundamental principles of quantitative research, including some introduction to statistical analysis. Additionally, the workshop will cover measurement concepts, including reliability and validity, and how to assess and improve the quality of data.

Coursework

Activities will be carried out during the workshop.

Visiting Lecturer:
George Onofrei

About

George Onofrei is Senior Lecturer in Operations and Supply Chain Management, at Atlantic Technological University, Ireland. He has completed his PhD at UCD Smurfit Graduate Business School, Ireland in the area of Operations and Supply Chain Management. He served on the Board of the European Operations Management Association (EurOMA) and was the Vice-President of Global Manufacturing Research Group (GMRG). His research interests focus on supply chain practices, sustainability, business data analytics and behavioural operations in manufacturing and service industries. His work has appeared in premier journals including International Journal of Production and Operations Management, Journal of Business Research, Business Strategy and the Environment, Supply Chain Management: An International Journal, Production Planning and Control, Resource Conservation and Recycling, International Journal of Production Research, Total Quality Management and Business Excellence, Operations Management Research and many more. He is a recipient of Lean Business Ireland Award (2019) for the Best Contribution to Lean/Operational Excellence Body of Work and the Irish Research Council Alty Award (2021).

Courses are open to the participation of all PhD students registered in Bursa Uludag University Social Sciences Institute. Certificates of participants will be provided to PhD students who attend the courses. Please fill in the form for registration.

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REGISTRATION LINK

VISITING LECTURE

REMODEL Visiting Lecture
for Bursa Uludag University PhD Students

Funded by
the European Union

March 19th, 2025
Time: 17:00 - 19:00

ONLINE

AI Powered Insights: Analyzing Visual and Textual Content on Social Media for Destination Marketing Management

- Understand the role of AI in analyzing social media content for tourism research.
- Identify key data sources and extraction techniques, including web scraping.
- Explain how text analysis, image recognition, and metadata analysis contribute to destination marketing strategies.
- Recognize ethical considerations and best practices in handling social media data.
- Apply basic AI-driven approaches to identify trends and engagement patterns in user-generated content.

Description

This course will introduce the key aspects of my doctoral thesis, titled AI-Powered Insights: Analyzing Visual and Textual Content on Social Media for Destination Marketing Management. The session will explore how artificial intelligence, machine learning, and deep learning techniques can be used to analyze user-generated content from social media platforms. It will cover how text, images, and metadata are processed to extract insights about tourist behavior, engagement patterns, and destination attractiveness. Attendees will gain an understanding of how AI-powered methodologies can improve destination marketing strategies by leveraging social media data.

Coursework

- Introduction to AI in tourism research – Overview of AI applications in destination marketing.
- Data collection techniques – Explanation of web scraping and data extraction from platforms like Instagram.
- Text and image analysis – Demonstration of natural language processing and computer vision methods used in tourism analytics.
- Engagement metrics and insights – Understanding social media engagement through AI-based analysis.
- Ethical considerations – Discussion on data privacy, ethical AI practices, and responsible research guidelines.
- Practical case study – Hands-on demonstration of an AI-powered analysis of user-generated content from social media.

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Visiting Lecturer:
Sofia Blanco Moreno

About

Sofía Blanco-Moreno is a Marketing and Tourism expert with a specialization in Digital Marketing and technologies such as Web Scraping and Artificial Intelligence (Machine Learning and Deep Learning) applied in Tourism and Hospitality. She is also an assistant professor at the University of León (Spain), and she has worked as a Digital Marketing expert on international companies such as Meliá Hotels. She has received several research awards, such as the best communication at the AIRSI and AIM 2023 conferences, I UAM-ASSECO Business Case Award 2022 and "Proof of concept" within the University-Business Knowledge Transfer Plan for the platform Photo Data Tour Analytics. Regarding her professional training, she has taught web scraping and artificial intelligence analysis courses at different universities such as Lleida, Zaragoza, Valencia and Valladolid, as well as in the REDINTUR network and the European university EURECA.

Courses are open to the participation of all PhD students registered in Bursa Uludag University Social Sciences Institute.
Certificates of participants will be provided to PhD students who attend the courses.
Please fill in the form for registration.

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REGISTRATION LINK

VISITING LECTURE

REMODEL Visiting Lecture
for Bursa Uludag University PhD Students

Funded by
the European Union

March 20th, 2025
Time: 17:00 - 19:00

ONLINE

Nature or City? A Neuroscientific Perspective on Emotion, Cognition, and Personality in Destination Marketing

Description

This workshop will present two consumer neuroscience studies applied to tourism marketing: one focusing on a nature-based destination (Australia) and the other on an urban destination (New York). The session will explore how both conscious and non-conscious responses—such as emotional impact, specific emotions, attention, and memory—towards promotional destination spots influence tourists' travel intentions and decision-making. Additionally, the workshop will examine the role of individual personality traits in shaping emotional responses and visual attention patterns. Finally, practical implications for tourism businesses and destinations will be discussed, providing key insights on how to structure tourism promotional videos to maximize their effectiveness.

Learning Outcomes

- Understand the impact of consumer neuroscience in tourism marketing.
- Identify the role of personality in emotional and visual responses.
- Apply practical insights to tourism promotion strategies.

Attendees are required to have a laptop with a stable Wi-Fi connection to follow the online session successfully.

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Visiting Lecturer:
Aroa Costa Feito

About

Dr. Aroa Costa Feito is an assistant professor and researcher at the University of León (Spain), specializing in consumer neuroscience, with a particular focus on the tourism industry and behavioural change for biodiversity conservation. Her research employs advanced neurophysiological tools, including eye-tracking, electroencephalography (EEG), and galvanic skin response (GSR), to analyse consumer behaviour and its impact on decision-making processes. Currently, she is actively involved in several European research projects, focusing on the practical application of scientific knowledge to generate a meaningful impact. She is an active member of the Society for Conservation Biology (Conservation Marketing group), the World Wildlife Fund (WWF), and the Spanish Marketing Association (AEMARK), aiming to promote behavioural change for biodiversity conservation.

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VISITING LECTURE

REMODEL Visiting Lecture
for Bursa Uludag University PhD Students

Funded by
the European Union

May 27th, 2025
Time: 13:30 - 15:00

BUU İİBF C BLOK
MAVİ SALON

Understanding Horizon Europe - Funding, Priorities & Participation

Learning Outcomes

- Understand the objectives and structure of Horizon Europe.
- Become familiar with the thematic clusters
- Explore Widening Participation & ERA
- Align Projects with EU Priorities

Description

This workshop offers an introduction to Horizon Europe, the EU's main research and innovation funding programme. Participants will explore its three key pillars, the six thematic clusters, and the focus on Widening Participation and Strengthening the European Research Area (ERA). The session will cover fundamental aspects of the programme, practical insights on engaging stakeholders, building strong partnerships, and aligning project ideas with EU priorities.

Atlantic
Technological
University

Visiting Professor:
Juanita Blue

About

Juanita Blue is Atlantic Technological University's Senior European Project Officer. She has extensive experience as a Programme Manager, leading and managing European funded projects under Horizon, Interreg, and Erasmus+. She advises researchers how to successfully access EU funding, and how to manage awarded projects. She also manages various EU funded projects across multiple disciplines on behalf of ATU. She holds a B.Sc. (hons) in Computer Security & Digital Forensics. As part of her ongoing Ph.D., she has conducted extensive research in the areas of Intelligent Identity Authentication and Intelligent Agents. Her work has been disseminated at forums both nationally and internationally. Juanita is an accomplished lecturer in the areas of Computer Security; Risk, Governance & Compliance; Biometrics; and Maths for Cryptography. Juanita specialises in projects with a digital theme and digital transformation technologies, and has extensive knowledge and experience in the area of sustainability and SDG education/implementation.

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REGISTRATION LINK

VISITING LECTURE

REMODEL Visiting Lecture
for Bursa Uludag University PhD Students

Funded by
the European Union

May 27th, 2025
Time: 10:00 - 11:30

BUU İİBF C BLOK
MAVİ SALON

Beyond Green: Exploring Sustainability's Deep Dimensions - Theory, Praxis and Navigating the Complexities for a Resilient Future

Learning Outcomes

- Critically analyse and compare advanced theoretical frameworks in sustainability science, including ecological economics, systems thinking, and socio-ecological systems approaches, evaluating their strengths, limitations, and applicability to diverse real-world challenges
- Evaluate cutting-edge research and frontier challenges in sustainability, such as the role of emerging technologies, novel governance models, and behavioural dimensions in driving or hindering sustainability transitions
- Apply a multi-dimensional perspective to sustainability case studies, identifying the intricate interplay of environmental, social and economic factors, and proposing evidence-based solutions informed by theoretical understanding
- Formulate relevant impactful research questions to address current knowledge gaps and pressing challenges in sustainability, demonstrating a readiness to contribute to the field at doctoral level

Description

This session offers an advanced exploration of sustainability, delving into complex socio-ecological systems through theoretical frameworks and critical analysis—from Brundtland's definition to Ostrom's commons governance and planetary boundaries in ecological economics. Engaging with cutting-edge research, emerging technologies, and innovative governance, participants will examine the behavioural and systemic dimensions of sustainability transitions through case studies. Designed to sharpen analytical tools and inspire impactful research, the session aims to provoke new questions and deepen commitment to the sustainability agenda.

Atlantic
Technological
University

Visiting Professor:
Ciarán Ó'hannracháin

About

Dr Ciarán Ó'hannracháin is a Faculty of Business Strategic Projects Manager at Atlantic Technological University (ATU) with a focus on Research & Collaboration Projects and holds the Operational Board Chair of the World Technology Universities Network (WTUN), a global network of universities focussed on delivering on the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Previous roles include Project Manager for Academic Planning and Strategy, Internationalisation and External Engagement during the creation of ATU.

Ciarán has also held Senior Academic Management positions in the Irish, UK, US and Swiss education systems, and lectures in Hospitality and Tourism Management. His research interests include both Education (Global HE Policy and Internationalisation of HE) and Business (Sustainable Regional Development, Business Model Innovation, Talent Management and Staff Training and Development).

Courses are open to the participation of all PhD students registered in Bursa Uludag University Social Sciences Institute. Certificates of participants will be provided to PhD students who attend the courses. Please fill in the form for registration.

Visit Our Website:
www.projectremodel.eu

REGISTRATION LINK

ANNEX 2. Visiting Lecture Activities on Social Media

remodel_project REMODEL first staff exchange activity under WP3 has been successfully organised at @uludaguniversitesi. Dr Conor McTiernan PhD from @atu_ie visited @buusosbilenstitu Management&Organization and Business Administration PhD classes for two days. Our students were very interactive and interested in topics. 🙌🙌🙌
REMODEL Staff Exchange activities and visiting lectures for BUU PhD classes will be re-organized in November, 2023.
#horizoneurope #widera #remodelproject #innovation #visitinglecturer #phdstudents #trust #knowledgemanagement
Düzenlendi · 20h Çevirisine bak

Remodel Project · 1.
Funded by the European Union
5 ay · Düzenlendi ·

REMODEL first staff exchange activity under WP3 has been successfully organized. Dr Conor McTiernan PhD from ATU Donegal Faculty of Business visited BUU Management&Organization and Business Administration PhD classes for two days. Our students were very interactive and interested in topics. Teamworks and discussions were also provided at the end of the lectures.

REMODEL Staff Exchange activities and visiting lectures for BUU PhD classes will be re-organized in November, 2023.
#business #remodel #horizoneurope #phd #visitinglecture #staffexchange #widera

Çeviriyi gör

Remodel Project · 1.
Funded by the European Union
6 ay ·

✦ Another successful REMODEL Staff Exchange has come to an end at Bursa Uludag Universitesi Faculty of Economics and Administrative Sciences!

✦ Special thanks to **HÉCTOR ALAIZ MORETÓN** and **Jose Alberto Benítez Andrades** from **Universidad de León**, Spain, for their invaluable contributions and for sharing their knowledge with our PhD students. Their participation has significantly enriched our project and inspired everyone involved. 🙌🙌

#horizoneurope #internationalcollaboration #innovation #datamining #bus

Çeviriyi göster

Three successful REMODEL Staff Exchange activities have wrapped up at Bursa Uludag University Faculty of Economics and Administrative Sciences!

Special thanks to **Aroa Costa-Feito** and **Sofía Blanco** from **Universidad de León** and **Tena Patten** from **Atlantic Technological University** for their invaluable contributions and knowledge sharing with our PhD students and early stage researchers.

Your participation has greatly enriched our project and inspired everyone involved!

#REMODEL #StaffExchange #Inspiration #KnowledgeSharing

Çeviriyi göster

ANNEX 3. Summer Schools on Social Media

Remodel Project · 1.
Funded by the European Union
6 gün · 🌐

...

✚ At the **Remodel Project** Summer School, held on 16–17 September at Bursa Uludağ University, we were delighted to welcome inspiring contributions from our sister projects.

💛 **Antonella Fresca**, partner of the **#SECReTOUR** project, presented the project's vision and outcomes, highlighting valuable synergies with REMODEL.

🌍 **Juanita Blue** introduced our other sister project, **VERNE Project**, which attracted strong interest and engagement from participants.

These exchanges demonstrated once again how collaboration across Horizon Europe projects creates opportunities to share knowledge, connect communities, and multiply impact. 🚀

#HorizonEurope #REMODEL #SECReTOUR #VERNE #Innovation #

Çeviriyi göster

ANNEX 4. Summer Schools Leaflets, Posters and News

SUMMER SCHOOL SUSTAINABILITY & TOURISM CHALLENGES

[PROJECTREMODELEU](https://projectremodel.eu)

Understanding and predicting consumer tourism responses: The synergy of implicit measures and AI

SUCH AN INSPIRATION FOR THE PARTICIPANTS AT REMODEL'S SUMMER SCHOOL

SPEAKER

THOMAS ZOËGA RAMSØY

Neurons Inc.

<https://thomasramsoy.com/>

SUMMER SCHOOL SUSTAINABILITY & TOURISM CHALLENGES

The science of experiences from a consumer neuromarketing approach

[PROJECTREMODELEU](https://projectremodel.eu)

MARKETERS HAVE AN EXCITING RANGE OF NEUROMARKETING TOOLS TO UNDERSTANDING CONSUMER EXPERIENCE. THE APPLICATION OF THIS NEW LENS IS ONLY LIMITED BY OUR SECTORS IMAGINATION.

SPEAKER

EDEL MOORE

University of Leeds, UK

SUMMER SCHOOL SUSTAINABILITY & TOURISM CHALLENGES

Mind the Gap: How to communicate
with the travellers of today

[PROJECTREMODELEU](https://projectremodel.eu)

*REFRESHING OUR IDEAS ON
BRAND MANAGEMENT IN THE
TOURISM SECTOR*

SPEAKER

DOLORES SEMERARO

Tourism Marketing Specialist, Keynote Speaker & Trainer

<https://doloressemeraro.com/>

SUMMER SCHOOL SUSTAINABILITY & TOURISM CHALLENGES

[PROJECTREMODELEU](https://projectremodel.eu)

*"I REALLY ENJOYED ENGAGING WITH
THE REMODEL SUMMER SCHOOL.
WITH SUSTAINABILITY BEING A
TRULY GLOBAL MEGATREND, IT'S
MORE IMPORTANT THAN EVER THAT
WE SHARE IDEAS OF HOW WE CAN
ALL MOVE TOWARDS LIVING
SUSTAINABLY"*

SPEAKER

NEIL RICHARDSON

Leeds Beckett University, UK

12th Wednesday

10.00-12.00
THOMAS ZOËGA RAMSØY
Neurons Inc.

Understanding and predicting consumer tourism responses: The synergy of implicit measures and AI
<https://thomasramsøy.com/>

13th Thursday

12.00-12.30 **Break**

12.30 - 14.30
EDEL MOORE
University of Leeds, UK
The science of experiences from a consumer neuromarketing approach

10.00 - 12.00
NEIL RICHARDSON
Leeds Beckett University, UK
Adapting models and frameworks to incorporate TBL-based sustainability

12.00-12.30 **Break**

12.30-14.30
DOLORES SEMERARO
Tourism Marketing Specialist, Keynote Speaker & Trainer
Mind the Gap: How to communicate with the travellers of today
<https://doloressemeraro.com/>

ATU Donegal Summer School: Sustainable Rural Tourism

6-7th
June 2024

Supporting sustainable tourism & hospitality in rural and peripheral areas requires contextual solutions to distinct challenges. Our Summer School will focus on exploring best practice in tourism and hospitality research, and consider contemporary models for supporting the sector in a rural area in Ireland.

Join us to hear from leading experts.

6th June

Registration 09.00 – 09.30

Workshops 09.30 – 16.00

Walking Tour 17.00 – 18.00

7th June

09.00 – 13.00

Site visits to include:

Radisson Blu Hotel, Letterkenny

Glenveagh National Park

FREE EVENT

Meet the Editor
– Demystifying
the publication
process

Opportunities
and benefits of
Hospitality GSTC
Certification

10 Years of the
Wild Atlantic
Way

Introducing
Ireland's only
Sustainable
Tourism
Observatory

Food and
Beverage
tourism- trends,
challenges and
opportunities

Prof Thomas
Fletcher, Managing
Editor Leisure
Studies

Dr Mihee Kang,
Global Assurance
and Asia Pacific
Director GSTC

Charlene Boyle,
Wild Atlantic Way
Officer, Fáilte
Ireland

Dr James Hanrahan,
Director ASTOI, PI
@ www.storyatu.ie
ATU Sligo

Jacinta Dalton,
Head of Dept
Culinary Arts, ATU
Galway

To book your place, please go to:

<https://forms.office.com/e/bV10RTIHG6>

SUMMER SCHOOL

16-17 SEPTEMBER 2025

INNOVATIVE BUSINESS SOLUTIONS AT HOSPITALITY SECTOR

Day 1 – September 16, 2025 (Turkish)

- Innovative Business Models in Restaurants
- Segmentation, Positioning, and Brand Management
- Cost Control and Profitability
- Interactive Value Proposition Canvas Workshop

Day 2 – September 17, 2025 (English and Turkish)

- Presentation of Successful EU Projects in the Service Sector
- New Funding Opportunities Offered by the EC.
- Horizon Europe Project Proposal Preparation and Application Process
- Experience Sharing with EU Project Coordinators
- Networking and Connection Session

Funded by
the European Union

Venue: Bursa Uludağ Üniversitesi
İktisadi ve İdari Bilimler Fakültesi
B Blok Bordo Salon
Time: 10:00 - 16:00

Investigadores del proyecto europeo Remodel se reúnen en Económicas

El rector Juan Francisco García Marín, ha recibido esta mañana en el iLab a los representantes de las universidades de Bursa (Turquía), Atlantic Technological (Irlanda) y León que participan en este consorcio cuyo objetivo es fortalecer las habilidades de Investigación e Innovación para avanzar en modelos de negocio en Turquía

Leonoticias
León

Lunes, 10 de julio 2023, 14:32

<https://www.leonoticias.com/universidad/investigadores-proyecto-europeo-remodel-reunen-economicas-20230710143242-nt.html>

1/9

Tu Nueva Crónica

PERSONALIZA LA INFORMACIÓN

Las noticias por geolocalización o tema.

ACTUALIDAD

IR

Ical | 26/06/2023 A A

La ULE recibirá en julio al consorcio del proyecto europeo 'Remodel'

UNIVERSIDAD En el iLab también participará la Universidad de Bursa (Turquía)

El iLab de la Facultad de Ciencias Económicas y Empresariales de la Universidad de León acogerá los próximos días 10 y 11 de julio una reunión del consorcio del proyecto europeo 'Remodel', en el que participa la **Atlantic Technological University** de Irlanda, la Universidad de Bursa (Turquía) y la ULE. El objeto del encuentro es analizar los seis primeros meses de trabajo de este proyecto y valorar la estrategia a desarrollar durante los próximos dos años y medio.

Extras

ENTRETENIMIENTO PARA TODOS LOS PÚBLICOS

León desde nuevos puntos de vista.

Recientes + Leídas Relacionadas

Un curso analizará la sostenibilidad alimentaria de la montaña leonesa

Autorizada la exhumación en Primout para identificar a una víctima del franquismo

Educar desde las imágenes: el libro renacentista

Desde el corazón de León para expandir latidos

Su niño y los otros niños

BURSA ULUDAĞ ÜNİVERSİTESİ İKTİSADİ VE İDARI BİLİMLER FAKÜLTESİ - B BLOK - BORDO SALON		
REMODEL SUMMER SCHOOL		
16-EYLÜL 2025 1.GÜN		
10:00	Açılış&Hoşgeldiniz	Prof.Dr.Esra Karaca Prof.Dr.Aylin Poroy Arsoy
10:15	Sektörden Başarı Hikayeleri: Restoranlarda Yenilikçi Yaklaşımlar	Moderatör: Prof.Dr.Yücel Sayılar Konuşmacılar: Onur Özkul - Yemek ve Ötesi Adnan Nar - Girişli Balık Mehmet Ceylan- Ceylan Fınn
11:30	LOCALNUTLEG proje sunumu	Prof.Dr.Yasemin Şahan
11:50	Yiyecek içecek sektöründe iş modeli geliştirme	Prof.Dr.Çağatan Taşkın
13:00	Yiyecek içecek sektöründe bölümlendirme ve konumlandırma	Prof.Dr.Çağatan Taşkın
13:25	Yiyecek içecek sektöründe marka yönetimi	Doç.Dr.Onur Öztürk
13:45	Yiyecek içecek sektöründe maliyet kontrolü ve karlılık	Prof.Dr.Ahmet Türel Prof.Dr.Aslı Türel
14:30	Değer önerisi kanvası çalıştayı	Doç. Dr. Mehlika Saraç Dr. Alp Aytac
15:40	Soru&cevap Tartışma	Moderatör: Prof.Dr.Yakup Selvi
16:00	1.gün kapanışı	

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BURSA ULUDAĞ ÜNİVERSİTESİ İKTİSADİ VE İDARI BİLİMLER FAKÜLTESİ - B BLOK - BORDO SALON		
REMODEL SUMMER SCHOOL		
17-EYLÜL 2025 2.GÜN		
10:00	Horizon Europe ve diğer AB güncel proje çağrıları (2026-2027 taslak çalışma programları)	Prof.Dr.Aylin Poroy Arsoy
10:30	Horizon Europe proje teklifi hazırlama ve başvuru süreci	Prof.Dr.Aylin Poroy Arsoy
11:20	REMODEL proje sunumu	Ciaran O'Hannracháin
11:40	VERNE proje sunumu	Juanita Blue
13:00	Proje sunumları: -DIGIFABS -FUSE -3 Kitchens -Food Eco Culture Edu -Waste 2 Worth -Ethical Food Entrepreneurship	Orla Casey
13:45	Proje sunumları: -FoodEducators -Kitchen Adventure -Kitchen Adventure app and GreenChef game	Viktoria Saas
14:15	SECreTOUR proje sunumu (sister project)	Antonella Fresa
15:00	Proje önerilerinin bütçe ve proje yönetiminin tartışılması Ağ oluşturma	Prof.Dr.Aylin Poroy Arsoy Prof.Dr.Elif Yücel Prof.Dr.Yasemin Ertan
16:00	Kapanış	

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BURSA ULUDAĞ ÜNİVERSİTESİ
FACULTY OF ECONOMIC AND ADMINISTRATIVE SCIENCES

50
YIL

ÜNİVERSİTE - AKADEMİK - ARAŞTIRMA - KAMPÜS - ÖĞRENCİ - HES

BUÜ'DE 'REMODEL SUMMER SCHOOL' ETKİNLİĞİ DÜZENLENDİ

Bursa Uludağ Üniversitesi (BUÜ) Ar-Ge Koordinatörlüğü ve Horizon Europe projesi olan REMODEL ekibi işbirliğinde "Summer School" etkinliği gerçekleştirildi. İktisadi ve İdari Bilimler Fakültesinde gerçekleşen programda, gıda ve içecek sektöründe iş modellerinin yanı sıra başarı hikayeleri ve Avrupa Birliği (AB) proje fırsatları ele alındı.

Etkinlik, BUÜ Ar-Ge Koordinatörü Prof. Dr. Esra Karaca ve İİBF İşletme Bölümü Öğretim Üyesi Prof. Dr. Aylin Poroy Arsoy'un açılış konuşmalarıyla başladı. Programa dair bilgi veren Prof. Dr. Poroy, "REMODEL projesi üniversitemizin ilk Horizon Europe koordinatörlüğü ve bizim gözbebeğimizdir. Şu ana kadar başarılı sonuçlara ulaştık ve hiçbir problem yaşamadık" dedi. Ar-Ge Koordinatörü Prof. Dr. Esra Karaca da proje ekibinin üniversiteye dış kaynaklardan yüksek bütçeler kazandırdığını belirterek, bu katkılardan dolayı kendilerine teşekkür etti.

SEKTÖRÜN BAŞARILI İSİMLERİ DENEYİMLERİNİ PAYLAŞTI

Program, Prof. Dr. Yücel Sayılar'ın moderatörlüğünü yaptığı panelle devam etti. Sosyal sorumluluk projesi "Yemek ve Ötesi"nin kurucusu Onur Özkul, Girişli Balık Restoranı'nın sahibi Adnan Nar ve Ceylan Fınn'ın sahibi Mehmet Ceylan, sektördeki başarı hikayelerini katılımcılarla paylaştı.

Etkinliğin devamında Prof. Dr. Yasemin Şahan, Prof. Dr. Çağatan Taşkın, Prof. Dr. Ahmet Türel, Prof. Dr. Aslı Türel, Doç. Dr. Onur Öztürk, Doç. Dr. Mehlika Saraç ve Dr. Alp Aytac da iş modeli geliştirme, marka yönetimi ve maliyet kontrolü gibi konularda bilgilerini aktardı. Sunumların ardından, Prof. Dr. Yakup Selvi'nin moderatörlüğünde soru-cevap bölümü düzenlendi.

ULUSLARARASI PROJELER ODAK NOKTASI OLDU

Programın ikinci gününde ise AB projeleri masaya yatırıldı. Prof. Dr. Aylin Poroy Arsoy, Horizon Europe'un yeni taslak programı hakkında bilgi vererek proje teklifi hazırlama süreçlerini anlattı. Etkinliğe katılan Ciaran O'Hannracháin, Juanita Blue, Orla Casey, Viktoria Saas, Antonella Fresa gibi uluslararası konuşmacılar, fonlanmış projelerden örnekler sunarak katılımcıları aydınlattı.

Katılımcıların kendi proje fikirlerini tartışabilecekleri serbest bir oturumun gerçekleştirildiği program, birebir danışmanlık görüşmeleriyle sona erdi.

Tüm Haberler